

New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By DOUBLE DOMINATION

Dr. Henry Garrett ◦ Independent Researcher ◦ Department of Mathematics ◦ DrHenryGarrett@gmail.com ◦ Manhattan, NY, USA

1 SYNOPSIS

In this scientific research, (Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION). Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $A_s = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then A_s is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION if the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION criteria holds.

$$\begin{aligned} & |(\sum_{V_i \in A_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} F(V_i))| \\ & = \min_{B_s \subseteq V_{NSHG}} \{ |(\sum_{V_i \in B_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} F(V_i))| \\ & \text{It's a dominating set and,} \\ & |N[v] \cap B_s| \geq 2, \text{ for every } v \in V. \\ & \} \end{aligned}$$

In this scientific research, new configurations are introduced for the new SuperHyperNotions, namely a DOUBLE DOMINATION and a Neutrosophic DOUBLE DOMINATION. Two different SuperHyperDefinitions were started for them, but research has progressed and SuperHyperNotion, SuperHyperUniform, and SuperHyperClass are well-defined and well-reviewed based on them. Literature review is implemented throughout this research. To shine the light and importance of this research, a comparison between this SuperHyperNotion with other SuperHyperNotions and basic SuperHyperNumbers is presented. Definitions are followed by examples and examples, so clarifications are guided by various tools. Applications are designed to understand the theoretical aspect of this ongoing research. “Cancer diagnosis” are the things that are being researched to explore the challenges that make sense in ongoing research and future research. It is a special case. Cells are viewed in the intended manner. There are different types of them. Some are individual and some are well modeled by groups of cells. All these types are officially called “SuperHyperVertex”, but the relationships between them all are officially called “SuperHyperEdge”. “SuperHyperGraph” and “Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph” frameworks are selected and selected for research on “Cancer Diagnosis”. Thus, these complex and dense super-hypermodels open avenues for research on theoretical aspects and “cancer diagnosis”. Ways to pursue this scientific research have been considered. It has also been formally collected in the form of several questions and problems. It is useful to define a “neutrosophic” version of DOUBLE DOMINATION. Since there are more ways to get type results a DOUBLE DOMINATION becomes more understandable. In order to master the Neutrosophic DOUBLE DOMINATION, there is a need to “re-define” the concept of “DOUBLE DOMINATION

mastery”. SuperHyperVertices and SuperHyperEdges are assigned by alphabetical labels. In this method, the position of tags is used to assign values. Suppose a DOUBLE DOMINATION. If the specified table contains “values of vertices, supervertices, edges, hyperedges, and hyperedges belonging to Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph” with key points, it is redefined. ”values of vertices & number of positions in alphabet”, ”Values of SuperVertices&maximum values of its vertices”, ”values of edges&maximum values of its vertices”, ”super edge values&max values of its vertices”, “super edge values” and maximum values of its endpoints”. To get examples and structural examples, I would like to introduce the next SuperHyperClass SuperHyperGraph based on DOUBLE DOMINATION. This is the original. Having the foundation of the previous definition in the SuperHyperClass type would be disciplined. If there is a need to have all DOUBLE DOMINATION until DOUBLE DOMINATION, then it is officially called “DOUBLE DOMINATION”, but otherwise, it is not DOUBLE DOMINATION. There is some explanation for the original definition titled “DOUBLE DOMINATION”. These two examples are further explored and distinguished because they are characterized in the SuperHyperClass disciplinary methods based on a dominant DOUBLE DOMINATION. Because of having DOUBLE DOMINATION, there is a need to “re-define” the concept of “neutrosophic DOUBLE DOMINATION” and “neutrosophic DOUBLE DOMINATION”. SuperHyperVertices and SuperHyperEdges are assigned by alphabetical labels. In this method, the position of tags is used to assign values. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. “Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph” is redefined if the desired table exists. And if the desired table exists, a DOUBLE DOMINATION is redefined to a “Neutrosophic DOUBLE DOMINATION”. It is useful to define a “Neutrosophic” version of SuperHyperClasses. Since there are more ways to obtain Neutrosophic type results, a SuperHyper- Neutrosophic DOUBLE DOMINATION becomes more understandable. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. If the desired table exists, there are a number of Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses. So are SuperHyperPath, SuperHyperCycle, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultiPartite and SuperHyperWheel. ”Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath”, “Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle”, “Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar”, “Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite”, “Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultiPartite” and “Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel”. A graph is SuperHyperUniform if it is a SuperHyperGraph and the number of SuperHyperEdges elements is the same. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. There are a number of SuperHyperClasses as follows. It is a SuperHyperPath if there is only one SuperVertex as an intersection between two given SuperHyperEdges with two exceptions. If only one SuperVertex is given as an intersection between two SuperHyperEdges, it is SuperHyperCycle. It is SuperHyperStar and only one SuperVertex as intersection among all SuperHyperEdges. It is SuperHyperBipartite, and only one SuperVertex is given as the intersection between two SuperHyperEdges, and these SuperVertices, which form two distinct sets, have no SuperHyperEdge in common. This is SuperHyperMultiPartite. Only one SuperVertex is given as an intersection between two SuperHyperEdges, and these SuperVertices, which form separate multisets, have no SuperHyperEdge in common. If only one SuperHyperEdge among the given two SuperHyperEdges is a SuperHyperWheel and a SuperVertex has a SuperHyperEdge with any regular SuperVertex. SuperHyperModel suggests specific designs and specific architectures. SuperHyperModel is officially called “SuperHyperGraph” and “Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph”. In this SuperHyperModel, the “special” cells and the “special group” of cells are SuperHyperModeled as “SuperHyperVertices” and the common and desired properties between the “special” cells and the “special group” of cells. SuperHyperModeled as “SuperHyperEdges”. Sometimes, to have a more accurate SuperHyperModel, it is useful to have some degree of determinism, uncertainty, and neutrality, in this case the SuperHyperModel is called “Neutrosophic”. In future scientific research, the foundation will be based on “diagnosis

of cancer” and the results and definitions will be introduced in redeemed methods. Cancer diagnosis in long-term practice. The specific region is assigned by the model (called SuperHyperGraph) and the long cycle of movement of the cancer is determined by this scientific research. Sometimes the movement of cancer is not easy to detect, because there is certainty, uncertainty and neutrality about the movements and effects of cancer on that area. This event leads us to choose another model [which is said to be the Neutrosophic superhypergraph] in order to have a proper understanding of what happened and was done. There are some specific models, which are well known and have names, and some SuperHyperGeneral SuperHyperModels. The movements and effects of cancer in complex pathways and between complex groups of cells can be visualized with a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (-/SuperHyperCycle, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel). The goal is to find the longest DOUBLE DOMINATION or the strongest DOUBLE DOMINATION in those Neutrosophic SuperHyperModels. Some general results are presented for the longest DOUBLE DOMINATION called DOUBLE DOMINATION and the strongest DOUBLE DOMINATION called Neutrosophic DOUBLE DOMINATION. Beyond that in SuperHyperStar, all possible SuperHyperPaths have only two SuperHyperEdges, but it is not enough as having at least three SuperHyperEdges is necessary to form any style of cycle. There is no form of any cycle, but literally, it is the transformation of any cycle. It literally transforms and does not form. A basic introduction to the theory of DOUBLE DOMINATION Neutrosophic, SuperHyperGraphs and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs is suggested.

Keywords: Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph, SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION, Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition

AMS Subject Classification: 05C17, 05C22, 05E45

2 Applied Notions Under The Scrutiny Of The Motivation Of This Scientific Research

In this scientific research, there are ideas in the prominent frameworks of motivations. I try to bring motivations in narrative ways. Some Cells have faced attacks from the established situation with cancer attacks in this case, there is some analysis embedded in the case current situations where cells can be labeled as some groups and some groups or individuals are overlabeled, all from behaviors to overcome cancer attacks. In embedded situations, cell individuals and cell groups can be considered as “new groups”. So it encourages us to find suitable SuperHyperModels for more appropriate analysis about this dirty story. I found SuperHyperModels, officially called “SuperHyperGraphs” and “Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. In this SuperHyperModel, cells and groups of cells are defined as “SuperHyperVertices” and relationships between individual cells and groups of cells are defined as “SuperHyperEdges”. So this is another motivation for us to do research on this SuperHyperModel based on “cancer diagnosis”. Sometimes, things get worse. The situation has passed certainty and precise style. So it is beyond them. There are three descriptions, i.e., degrees of determination, uncertainty, and neutrality, for any object based on ambiguous forms, i.e., incomplete data, imprecise data, and uncertain analysis. The second model can be considered in the previous SuperHyperModel. This is SuperHyperModel. This is SuperHyperGraph but officially called “Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Cancer is a disease, but the model is supposed to understand what happens in this phenomenon. The special case of this disease is considered and some parameters are used as consequences of the model. Cells are attacked by the disease, but the movement of cancer is in a specific area. Knowing the mind of cancer can help to find some cures for this disease. SuperHyperGraph and

Neutrosophic Super-HyperGraph are super-hypermodels used in “cancer diagnosis” and both are the foundation of the background of this scientific research. Sometimes cancer has occurred in an area full of cells, cell groups, and embedded styles. In this section, SuperHyperModel proposes based on the links of cancer movements in the form of unity styles with the formation of design and architecture officially called “DOUBLE DOMINATION”, in the themes of specialized terms and common words. Particle for direct object. Applied concepts under the investigation of the motivation of this scientific research. The “SuperHyper” prefix refers to the theme of embedded styles for background discovery for SuperHyperNotions. Cancer diagnosis in long-term practice. The specific region is assigned by the model (called SuperHyperGraph) and the long cycle of movement of the cancer is determined by this scientific research. Sometimes the movement of Cancer is not easy to identify because there is certainty, uncertainty and neutrality about the movements and effects of Cancer in that region. This event leads us to choose another model [said to be Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph]. Easy understanding of what happened and what was done. There are some specific models that are well known and named and some general models. The movements and effects of cancer in complex pathways and between complex groups of cells can be visualized by a neutrosophic superhyperpath (-/SuperHyperCycle, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultipartite, SuperHyperWheel). The goal is to find DOUBLE DOMINATION or Neutrosophic DOUBLE DOMINATION for SuperHyperModels in it. Some general results are presented. Beyond that in SuperHyperStar, all possible Neutrosophic SuperHyperPaths have only two SuperHyperEdges, but it is not enough as having at least three SuperHyperEdges is necessary to form any style of cycle. There is no form of cycle, but it is literally a form of any cycle. It literally transforms and does not form.

Question 2.1. *How to define “SuperHyperNotions and to do research” to find the “DOUBLE DOMINATION Rate” of any cell or groups of cells based on fixed cell or fixed group of cells broadly, “DOUBLE DOMINATION Rate” based on fixed groups or fixed cells. Groups of groups of cells?*

Question 2.2. *What are the best descriptions for “diagnosing cancer” in terms of these chaotic and dense super-hypermodels in which embedded concepts are depicted?*

This motivation to find concepts to use in this dense model is called “SuperHyperGraphs”. So it motivates us to define different types of “DOUBLE DOMINATION” and “neutrosophic DOUBLE DOMINATION” over “superhypergraph” and “neutrosophic superhypergraph”. Then this scientific research has taken more motivations to define SuperHyperClasses and find some connections among this SuperHyperNotion with other SuperHyperNotions. It motivates us to obtain examples and examples to clarify the framework of this scientific research. The general results and some of the results about some of the connections are the ways that the key point of this scientific research, “diagnosis of cancer” is more understandable and clear.

The framework of this research is as follows. First, I will introduce the basic definitions to clarify the basics. In the “Introductions” subsection, basic definitions about SuperHyperGraphs and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph are introduced and discussed in depth. Basic concepts are thoroughly explained and illustrated, and sometimes a literature review is used to make sense of what is to come in the coming sections. The main definitions and their explanations, along with some results on the new concepts, DOUBLE DOMINATION and Neutrosophic DOUBLE DOMINATION, are specified in the sections “DOUBLE DOMINATION” and “Neutrosophic DOUBLE DOMINATION”. In the concept of dealing with results and in DOUBLE DOMINATION to create logic about the continuation of the scientific research, the ideas of SuperHyperUniform and Neutrosophic SuperHyperUniform are introduced and as their

consequences, the corresponding SuperHyperClasses are specified to summarize the work done in this section, as “Results on SuperHyperClasses” and “Results on Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses”. Going back to the core concepts, clever steps towards common concepts to extend new concepts in new frameworks, SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph, in “Results on SuperHyperClasses” and “Results on Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses” sections. There is the initial scientific research on supergeneral relations and as the final and final part of the theoretical scientific research is available in the section “General results”. Some general SuperHyperRelations are fundamental and are known as fundamental SuperHyperNotions, as in “General results” were extracted and discussed. “DOUBLE DOMINATION”, “Neutrosophic DOUBLE DOMINATION”, “Results on SuperHyperClasses” and “Results on Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses”. There are curious questions about what has been done about SuperHyperNotions to make sense of the superiority of this scientific research and to discover the word “best” as a description and adjective of this scientific research as presented in the “DOUBLE DOMINATION” section. The keyword of this scientific research was presented in the section “Applications in cancer diagnosis” with two cases and sub-sections “Case 1: Initial steps towards SuperHyperBipartite as SuperHyperModel” and “Case 2: Incremental steps towards SuperHyperMultiperdel as SuperHyper”. In the “open issues” section, there is a detailed examination and recognition of what was done in this scientific research and what happened in this scientific research in the form of “questions” and “issues” in order to understand this scientific research in an outstanding style, the advantages and limitations of this scientific research in addition to What has been done in this scientific research is stated in the “conclusion and final remarks” section.

3 Neutrosophic Preliminaries Of This Scientific Research On the Redeemed Ways

In this section, the basic material in this scientific research, is referred to [Single Valued Neutrosophic Set](Ref. [1],Definition 2.2,p.2), [Neutrosophic Set](Ref. [1],Definition 2.1,p.1), [Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)](Ref. [1],Definition 2.5,p.2), [Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)](Ref. [1],Definition 2.7,p.3), [t-norm](Ref. [1], Definition 2.7, p.3), and [Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)](Ref. [1],Definition 2.7,p.3), [Neutrosophic Strength of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPaths] (Ref. [1],Definition 5.3,p.7), and [Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)] (Ref. [1],Definition 5.4,p.7). Also, the new ideas and their clarifications are addressed to Ref. [1].

In this subsection, the basic material which is used in this scientific research, is presented. Also, the new ideas and their clarifications are elicited.

Definition 3.1 (Neutrosophic Set). (Ref. [1],Definition 2.1,p.1).

Let X be a Eulerian-Path-Cut of points (objects) with generic elements in X denoted by x ; then the **Neutrosophic set** A (NS A) is an object having the form

$$A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$$

where the functions $T, I, F : X \rightarrow]-0, 1^+[$ define respectively the a **truth-membership function**, an **indeterminacy-membership function**, and a **falsity-membership function** of the element $x \in X$ to the set A with the condition

$$-0 \leq T_A(x) + I_A(x) + F_A(x) \leq 3^+.$$

The functions $T_A(x)$, $I_A(x)$ and $F_A(x)$ are real standard or nonstandard subsets of $]^{-0}, 1^+]$.

Definition 3.2 (Single Valued Neutrosophic Set). (Ref. [1], Definition 2.2, p.2).

Let X be a Eulerian-Path-Cut of points (objects) with generic elements in X denoted by x . A **single valued Neutrosophic set** A (SVNS A) is characterized by truth-membership function $T_A(x)$, an indeterminacy-membership function $I_A(x)$, and a falsity-membership function $F_A(x)$. For each point x in X , $T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \in [0, 1]$. A SVNS A can be written as

$$A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}.$$

Definition 3.3. The **degree of truth-membership**, **indeterminacy-membership** and **falsity-membership of the subset** $X \subset A$ of the single valued Neutrosophic set $A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$:

$$T_A(X) = \min[T_A(v_i), T_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X},$$

$$I_A(X) = \min[I_A(v_i), I_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X},$$

$$F_A(X) = \min[F_A(v_i), F_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X}.$$

Definition 3.4. The **support** of $X \subset A$ of the single valued Neutrosophic set $A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$:

$$\text{supp}(X) = \{ x \in X : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) > 0 \}.$$

Definition 3.5 (Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)). (Ref. [1], Definition 2.5, p.2).

Assume V' is a given set. a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph** (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$, where

- (i) $V = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_n\}$ a finite set of finite single valued Neutrosophic subsets of V' ;
- (ii) $V = \{(V_i, T_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_i)) : T_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_i) \geq 0\}$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);
- (iii) $E = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_{n'}\}$ a finite set of finite single valued Neutrosophic subsets of V ;
- (iv) $E = \{(E_{i'}, T'_V(E_{i'}), I'_V(E_{i'}), F'_V(E_{i'})) : T'_V(E_{i'}), I'_V(E_{i'}), F'_V(E_{i'}) \geq 0\}$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$);
- (v) $V_i \neq \emptyset$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);
- (vi) $E_{i'} \neq \emptyset$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$);
- (vii) $\sum_i \text{supp}(V_i) = V$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);
- (viii) $\sum_{i'} \text{supp}(E_{i'}) = V$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$);
- (ix) and the following conditions hold:

$$T'_V(E_{i'}) \leq \min[T_{V'}(V_i), T_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}},$$

$$I'_V(E_{i'}) \leq \min[I_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}},$$

$$F'_V(E_{i'}) \leq \min[F_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_j)]_{V_i, V_j \in E_{i'}}$$

where $i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$.

Figure 1. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a illustrated SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Here the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $E_{j'}$ and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) V_j are single valued Neutrosophic sets. $T_{V'}(V_i)$, $I_{V'}(V_i)$, and $F_{V'}(V_i)$ denote the degree of truth-membership, the degree of indeterminacy-membership and the degree of falsity-membership the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V . $T'_V(E_{i'})$, $T''_V(E_{i'})$, and $T'''_V(E_{i'})$ denote the degree of truth-membership, the degree of indeterminacy-membership and the degree of falsity-membership of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E_{i'}$ to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) E . Thus, the ii' th element of the **incidence matrix** of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) are of the form $(V_i, T'_V(E_{i'}), I'_V(E_{i'}), F'_V(E_{i'}))$, the sets V and E are crisp sets.

Example 3.6. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$ in the mentioned Neutrosophic Figures in every Neutrosophic items.

- On the Figure (1), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic notion, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. E_1 and E_3 are some empty Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges but E_2 is a loop Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge and E_4 is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Neutrosophic isolated means that there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge has it as a Neutrosophic endpoint.
- On the Figure (2), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic notion, is up. The Neutrosophic Algorithm is Neutrosophically straightforward. E_1, E_2 and E_3 are some empty Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges but E_4 is a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex, V_3 is Neutrosophic isolated means that there's no Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge has it as a Neutrosophic endpoint.
- On the Figure (3), the SuperHyperNotion, namely, SuperHyperGirth, is up. E_1, E_2 and E_3 are some empty SuperHyperEdges but E_4 is a SuperHyperEdge. Thus in the terms of SuperHyperNeighbor, there's only one SuperHyperEdge, namely, E_4 .

Figure 2. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a illustrated SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 3. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a illustrated SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 4. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a illustrated SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

- On the Figure (4), there is no empty SuperHyperEdge but E_3 is a loop SuperHyperEdge on $\{F\}$ and there are some SuperHyperEdges, namely, E_1 on $\{H, V_1, V_3\}$, alongside E_2 on $\{O, H, V_4, V_3\}$ and E_4, E_5 on $\{N, V_1, V_2, V_3, F\}$. 280
281
282
- On the Figure (5), there is neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 283
284
- On the Figure (6), there is neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 285
286
- On the Figure (7), there is neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 287
288
- On the Figure (8), there is neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 289
290
- On the Figure (9), there is neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 291
292
- On the Figure (10), there is neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 293
294
- On the Figure (11), there is neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 295
296
- On the Figure (12), there is neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 297
298
- On the Figure (13), there is neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 299
300
- On the Figure (14), there is neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 301
302
- On the Figure (15), there is neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 303
304

Figure 5. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs mentioned as the SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 6. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a illustrated SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 7. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs depicted SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 8. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with dense SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 9. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a messy SuperHyper-Modeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 10. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with highly-embedding-connected SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 11. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 12. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with highly-multiple-connected-style SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 13. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 14. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 15. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with Linearly-Connected SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 16. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 17. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a Linearly-over-packed SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

- On the Figure (16), there is neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 305
306
- On the Figure (17), there is neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 307
308
- On the Figure (18), there is neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 309
310
- On the Figure (19), there is neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 311
312
- On the Figure (20), there is neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 313
314
- On the Figure (21), there is neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 315
316
- On the Figure (22), there is neither empty SuperHyperEdge nor loop SuperHyperEdge. 317
318

Definition 3.7 (Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)). 319
 (Ref. [1], Definition 2.7, p.3). 320

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) E_i ' and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) V_i of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) $S = (V, E)$ could be characterized as follow-up items. 321
322
323
324

(i) If $|V_i| = 1$, then V_i is called **vertex**; 325

(ii) if $|V_i| \geq 1$, then V_i is called **SuperVertex**; 326

Figure 18. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 19. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 20. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 21. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

Figure 22. The Connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs with a SuperHyperModeling on Recognition of Cancer in the Neutrosophic Example (3.6)

- (iii) if for all V_i s are incident in $E_{i'}$, $|V_i| = 1$, and $|E_{i'}| = 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **edge**; 327
- (iv) if for all V_i s are incident in $E_{i'}$, $|V_i| = 1$, and $|E_{i'}| \geq 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **HyperEdge**; 328
329
- (v) if there's a V_i is incident in $E_{i'}$ such that $|V_i| \geq 1$, and $|E_{i'}| = 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **SuperEdge**; 330
331
- (vi) if there's a V_i is incident in $E_{i'}$ such that $|V_i| \geq 1$, and $|E_{i'}| \geq 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **SuperHyperEdge**. 332
333

If we choose different types of binary operations, then we could get hugely diverse types of general forms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG). 334
335

Definition 3.8 (t-norm). (Ref. [1], Definition 2.7, p.3). 336

A binary operation $\otimes : [0, 1] \times [0, 1] \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is a **t-norm** if it satisfies the following for $x, y, z, w \in [0, 1]$: 337
338

- (i) $1 \otimes x = x$; 339
- (ii) $x \otimes y = y \otimes x$; 340
- (iii) $x \otimes (y \otimes z) = (x \otimes y) \otimes z$; 341
- (iv) If $w \leq x$ and $y \leq z$ then $w \otimes y \leq x \otimes z$. 342

Definition 3.9. The **degree of truth-membership, indeterminacy-membership and falsity-membership of the subset** $X \subset A$ of the single valued Neutrosophic set $A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$ (with respect to t-norm T_{norm}):

$$T_A(X) = T_{norm}[T_A(v_i), T_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X},$$

$$I_A(X) = T_{norm}[I_A(v_i), I_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X},$$

$$F_A(X) = T_{norm}[F_A(v_i), F_A(v_j)]_{v_i, v_j \in X}.$$

Definition 3.10. The **support** of $X \subset A$ of the single valued Neutrosophic set $A = \{ \langle x : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle, x \in X \}$:

$$\text{supp}(X) = \{x \in X : T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) > 0\}.$$

Definition 3.11. (General Forms of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)).

Assume V' is a given set. a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph** (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$, where

- (i) $V = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_n\}$ a finite set of finite single valued Neutrosophic subsets of V' ;
- (ii) $V = \{(V_i, T_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_i)) : T_{V'}(V_i), I_{V'}(V_i), F_{V'}(V_i) \geq 0\}$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);
- (iii) $E = \{E_1, E_2, \dots, E_{n'}\}$ a finite set of finite single valued Neutrosophic subsets of V ;
- (iv) $E = \{(E_{i'}, T'_{V'}(E_{i'}), I'_{V'}(E_{i'}), F'_{V'}(E_{i'})) : T'_{V'}(E_{i'}), I'_{V'}(E_{i'}), F'_{V'}(E_{i'}) \geq 0\}$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$);
- (v) $V_i \neq \emptyset$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);
- (vi) $E_{i'} \neq \emptyset$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$);
- (vii) $\sum_i \text{supp}(V_i) = V$, ($i = 1, 2, \dots, n$);
- (viii) $\sum_{i'} \text{supp}(E_{i'}) = V$, ($i' = 1, 2, \dots, n'$).

Here the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $E_{j'}$ and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) V_j are single valued Neutrosophic sets. $T_{V'}(V_i)$, $I_{V'}(V_i)$, and $F_{V'}(V_i)$ denote the degree of truth-membership, the degree of indeterminacy-membership and the degree of falsity-membership the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V . $T'_{V'}(E_{i'})$, $I'_{V'}(E_{i'})$, and $F'_{V'}(E_{i'})$ denote the degree of truth-membership, the degree of indeterminacy-membership and the degree of falsity-membership of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E_{i'}$ to the Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) E . Thus, the i 'th element of the **incidence matrix** of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) are of the form $(V_i, T'_{V'}(E_{i'}), I'_{V'}(E_{i'}), F'_{V'}(E_{i'}))$, the sets V and E are crisp sets.

Definition 3.12 (Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)). (Ref. [1], Definition 2.7, p.3).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE) $E_{i'}$ and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) V_i of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) $S = (V, E)$ could be characterized as follow-up items.

- (i) If $|V_i| = 1$, then V_i is called **vertex**;
- (ii) if $|V_i| \geq 1$, then V_i is called **SuperVertex**;
- (iii) if for all V_i s are incident in $E_{i'}$, $|V_i| = 1$, and $|E_{i'}| = 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **edge**;
- (iv) if for all V_i s are incident in $E_{i'}$, $|V_i| = 1$, and $|E_{i'}| \geq 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **HyperEdge**;
- (v) if there's a V_i is incident in $E_{i'}$ such that $|V_i| \geq 1$, and $|E_{i'}| = 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **SuperEdge**;

(vi) if there's a V_i is incident in $E_{i'}$ such that $|V_i| \geq 1$, and $|E_{i'}| \geq 2$, then $E_{i'}$ is called **SuperHyperEdge**.

This SuperHyperModel is too messy and too dense. Thus there's a need to have some restrictions and conditions on SuperHyperGraph. The special case of this SuperHyperGraph makes the patterns and regularities.

Definition 3.13. A graph is **SuperHyperUniform** if it's SuperHyperGraph and the number of elements of SuperHyperEdges are the same.

To get more visions on SuperHyperUniform, the some SuperHyperClasses are introduced. It makes to have SuperHyperUniform more understandable.

Definition 3.14. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. There are some SuperHyperClasses as follows.

- (i). It's **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath** if it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges with two exceptions;
- (ii). it's **SuperHyperCycle** if it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges;
- (iii). it's **SuperHyperStar** it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid all SuperHyperEdges;
- (iv). it's **SuperHyperBipartite** it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges and these SuperVertices, forming two separate sets, has no SuperHyperEdge in common;
- (v). it's **SuperHyperMultiPartite** it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges and these SuperVertices, forming multi separate sets, has no SuperHyperEdge in common;
- (vi). it's **SuperHyperWheel** if it's only one SuperVertex as intersection amid two given SuperHyperEdges and one SuperVertex has one SuperHyperEdge with any common SuperVertex.

Example 3.15. In the Figure (23), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath $ESH P : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (23), is the notion.

Example 3.16. In the Figure (24), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle $NSHC : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (24), is up.

Example 3.17. In the Figure (25), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, is highlighted and featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar $ESHS : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (25), is up.

Example 3.18. In the Neutrosophic Figure (26), the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, is Neutrosophic highlighted and Neutrosophic featured. The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Neutrosophic Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (26), is up.

Figure 23. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath Associated to the Notions in the Example (3.15)

Figure 24. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (3.16)

Figure 25. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (3.17)

Figure 26. Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Example (3.18)

SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)

$$V_1, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, \dots, V_{s-1}, E_{s-1}, V_s$$

is called a **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath** (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_1 to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_s if either of following conditions hold:

- (i) $V_i, V_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (ii) there's a vertex $v_i \in V_i$ such that $v_i, V_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (iii) there's a SuperVertex $V'_i \in V_i$ such that $V'_i, V_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (iv) there's a vertex $v_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $V_i, v_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (v) there's a SuperVertex $V'_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $V_i, V'_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (vi) there are a vertex $v_i \in V_i$ and a vertex $v_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $v_i, v_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (vii) there are a vertex $v_i \in V_i$ and a SuperVertex $V'_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $v_i, V'_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (viii) there are a SuperVertex $V'_i \in V_i$ and a vertex $v_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $V'_i, v_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$;
- (ix) there are a SuperVertex $V'_i \in V_i$ and a SuperVertex $V'_{i+1} \in V_{i+1}$ such that $V'_i, V'_{i+1} \in E_{i'}$.

Definition 3.22. (Characterization of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPaths).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_1 to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_s is sequence of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) and Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)

$$V_1, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, \dots, V_{s-1}, E_{s-1}, V_s,$$

could be characterized as follow-up items.

- (i) If for all $V_i, E_{j'}, |V_i| = 1, |E_{j'}| = 2$, then NSHP is called **path**;
- (ii) if for all $E_{j'}, |E_{j'}| = 2$, and there's $V_i, |V_i| \geq 1$, then NSHP is called **SuperPath**;
- (iii) if for all $V_i, E_{j'}, |V_i| = 1, |E_{j'}| \geq 2$, then NSHP is called **HyperPath**;
- (iv) if there are $V_i, E_{j'}, |V_i| \geq 1, |E_{j'}| \geq 2$, then NSHP is called **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath**.

Definition 3.23 (Neutrosophic Strength of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperPaths).

(Ref. [1], Definition 5.3, p.7).

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. A Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_1 to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_s is sequence of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices (NSHV) and Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)

$$V_1, E_1, V_2, E_2, V_3, \dots, V_{s-1}, E_{s-1}, V_s,$$

have

- (i) **Neutrosophic t-strength** $(\min\{T(V_i)\}, m, n)_{i=1}^s$;
- (ii) **Neutrosophic i-strength** $(m, \min\{I(V_i)\}, n)_{i=1}^s$;

Table 1. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph Mentioned in the Definition (3.27)

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

(iii) **Neutrosophic f-strength** $(m, n, \min\{F(V_i)\}_{i=1}^s$; 459

(iv) **Neutrosophic strength** $(\min\{T(V_i)\}, \min\{I(V_i)\}, \min\{F(V_i)\}_{i=1}^s$. 460

Definition 3.24 (Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdges (NSHE)). (Ref. [1], Definition 5.4, p.7). 461

Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) $E = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then E is called 463

(ix) **Neutrosophic t-connective** if $T(E) \geq$ maximum number of Neutrosophic t-strength of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$; 465

(x) **Neutrosophic i-connective** if $I(E) \geq$ maximum number of Neutrosophic i-strength of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$; 468

(xi) **Neutrosophic f-connective** if $F(E) \geq$ maximum number of Neutrosophic f-strength of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$; 471

(xii) **Neutrosophic connective** if $(T(E), I(E), F(E)) \geq$ maximum number of Neutrosophic strength of SuperHyperPath (NSHP) from Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_i to Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex (NSHV) V_j where $1 \leq i, j \leq s$. 474

For the sake of having a Neutrosophic notion, there's a need to "redefine" the notion of "Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph". The SuperHyperVertices and the SuperHyperEdges are assigned by the labels from the letters of the alphabets. In this procedure, there's the usage of the position of labels to assign to the values. 478

Definition 3.25. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (SHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. It's redefined **Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph** if the Table (1) holds. 482

It's useful to define a "Neutrosophic" version of SuperHyperClasses. Since there's more ways to get Neutrosophic type-results to make a Neutrosophic more understandable. 484

Definition 3.26. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (SHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$. There are some **Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses** if the Table (2) holds. Thus Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath, notion, SuperHyperStar, SuperHyperBipartite, SuperHyperMultiPartite, and SuperHyperWheel, are **Neutrosophic SuperHyperPath**, **Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle**, **Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar**, **Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite**, **Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultiPartite**, and **Neutrosophic SuperHyperWheel** if the Table (2) holds. 487

Table 2. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph, Mentioned in the Definition (3.26)

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

Table 3. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph Mentioned in the Definition (3.27)

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

It's useful to define a "Neutrosophic" version of a Neutrosophic notion. Since there's more ways to get type-results to make a Neutrosophic notion more Neutrosophicly understandable.

For the sake of having a Neutrosophic notion, there's a need to "redefine" the Neutrosophic notion of "Neutrosophic notion". The SuperHyperVertices and the SuperHyperEdges are assigned by the labels from the letters of the alphabets. In this procedure, there's the usage of the position of labels to assign to the values.

Definition 3.27. Assume a notion. It's redefined a **Neutrosophic notion** if the Table (3) holds.

Example 3.28. Referred to the Example (3.6), assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (SHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$ in the mentioned Neutrosophic Figures in every Neutrosophic items.

- On the Figure (1), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (4).
- On the Figure (2), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (5).
- On the Figure (3), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (6).
- On the Figure (4), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (7).

Table 4. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.13, 0.13, 0.13)	E_1	(0, 0, 0)
V_2	(0.13, 0.13, 0.13)	E_2	(0.13, 0.13, 0.13)
V_3	(0.15, 0.15, 0.15)	E_3	(0, 0, 0)
V_4	(0.14, 0.14, 0.14)	E_4	(0.14, 0.14, 0.14)

Table 5. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.13, 0.13, 0.13)	E_1	(0, 0, 0)
V_2	(0.03, 0.03, 0.03)	E_2	(0, 0, 0)
V_3	(0.15, 0.15, 0.15)	E_3	(0, 0, 0)
V_4	(0.14, 0.14, 0.14)	E_4	(0.14, 0.14, 0.14)

Table 6. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.13, 0.13, 0.13)	E_1	(0, 0, 0)
V_2	(0.11, 0.11, 0.11)	E_2	(0, 0, 0)
V_3	(0.14, 0.14, 0.14)	E_3	(0, 0, 0)
-	-	E_4	(0.14, 0.14, 0.14)

Table 7. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.13, 0.13, 0.13)	E_1	(0.08, 0.08, 0.08)
V_2	(0.11, 0.11, 0.11)	E_2	(0.15, 0.15, 0.15)
V_3	(0.05, 0.05, 0.05)	E_3	(0, 0, 0)
V_4	(0.12, 0.12, 0.12)	E_4	(0.14, 0.14, 0.14)
$\{F\}$	(0.06, 0.06, 0.06)	E_5	(0.14, 0.14, 0.14)
$\{H\}$	(0.08, 0.08, 0.08)	-	-
$\{N\}$	(0.14, 0.14, 0.14)	-	-
$\{O\}$	(0.15, 0.15, 0.15)	-	-

Figure 29. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.2)

4 Main Resultant

Definition 4.1. (Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION).

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $A_s = \{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_s\}$. Then A_s is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION if the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION criteria holds.

$$\begin{aligned} & |(\sum_{V_i \in A_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} F(V_i))| \\ & = \min_{B_s \subseteq V_{NSHG}} \{ |(\sum_{V_i \in B_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} F(V_i))| \} \end{aligned}$$

It's a dominating set and,

$$|N[v] \cap B_s| \geq 2, \text{ for every } v \in V.$$

}|.

Example 4.2. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite (SHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$ in the mentioned Neutrosophic Figures in every Neutrosophic items.

- On the Figure (29), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (8).

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$.

Assume SuperHyperPart $\{V_i\}_{i=1}^7$ and non-SuperHyperPart $\{V_i\}_{i=7}^{12}$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $A_s = \{V_i\}_{i=1,7-8,11-12}$. Then A_s is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION if the following expressions, terms

Figure 30. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.2)

Figure 31. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.2)

Figure 32. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.2)

Figure 33. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.2)

Figure 34. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.2)

Figure 35. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.2)

Figure 39. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.3)

Figure 40. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.3)

Figure 41. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.3)

Figure 42. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle Neutrosophic Associated to the Neutrosophic Notions in the Neutrosophic Example (4.3)

Table 8. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_5	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_6	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_7	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)

and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION criteria holds. 530
531

$$\begin{aligned}
 & |(\sum_{V_i \in A_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} F(V_i))| \\
 &= \min_{B_s \subseteq V_{NSHG}} \{(\sum_{V_i \in B_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} F(V_i))\} \\
 &\text{It's a dominating set and,} \\
 &|N[v] \cap B_s| \geq 2, \text{ for every } v \in V. \\
 &\} |.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (30), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (9). 532
533

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. 534
 Assume SuperHyperPart $\{V_i\}_{i=1}^7$ and non-SuperHyperPart $\{V_i\}_{i=7}^{12}$. Consider a 535

Table 9. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_5	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_6	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_7	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)

Table 10. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_5	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_6	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_7	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)

Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $A_s = \{V_i\}_{i=1-2,7-8,11-12}$. Then A_s is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION if the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION criteria holds.

$$|(\sum_{V_i \in A_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} F(V_i))|$$

$$= \min_{B_s \subseteq V_{NSHG}} |(\sum_{V_i \in B_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} F(V_i))|$$

It's a dominating set and,

$$|N[v] \cap B_s| \geq 2, \text{ for every } v \in V.$$

}|.

- On the Figure (31), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (10).

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume SuperHyperPart $\{V_i\}_{i=1}^7$ and non-SuperHyperPart $\{V_i\}_{i=7}^{12}$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $A_s = \{V_i\}_{i=1-3,7-8,11-12}$. Then A_s is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION if the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION criteria holds.

$$|(\sum_{V_i \in A_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} F(V_i))|$$

$$= \min_{B_s \subseteq V_{NSHG}} |(\sum_{V_i \in B_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} F(V_i))|$$

It's a dominating set and,

$$|N[v] \cap B_s| \geq 2, \text{ for every } v \in V.$$

}|.

- On the Figure (32), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (11).

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume SuperHyperPart $\{V_i\}_{i=1}^7$ and non-SuperHyperPart $\{V_i\}_{i=7}^{12}$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $A_s = \{V_i\}_{i=1-3,5,7-8,11-12}$. Then A_s is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION if the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION criteria holds.

$$|(\sum_{V_i \in A_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} F(V_i))|$$

Table 11. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_5	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)
V_6	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_7	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)

Table 12. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_5	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)
V_6	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	V_7	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)

$$= \min_{B_s \subseteq V_{NSHG}} \left| \left\{ \left(\sum_{V_i \in B_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} F(V_i) \right) \right\} \right|$$

It's a dominating set and,

$$|N[v] \cap B_s| \geq 2, \text{ for every } v \in V.$$

$$\left. \right\}.$$

- On the Figure (33), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (12). 556
557

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. 558
 Assume SuperHyperPart $\{V_i\}_{i=1}^7$ and non-SuperHyperPart $\{V_i\}_{i=7}^{12}$. Consider a 559
 Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $A_s = \{V_i\}_{i=1-3,5-8,11-12}$. Then A_s is called 560
 Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION if the following expressions, terms 561
 and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION criteria 562
 holds. 563

$$\left| \left(\sum_{V_i \in A_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} F(V_i) \right) \right|$$

$$= \min_{B_s \subseteq V_{NSHG}} \left| \left\{ \left(\sum_{V_i \in B_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} F(V_i) \right) \right\} \right|$$

It's a dominating set and,

$$|N[v] \cap B_s| \geq 2, \text{ for every } v \in V.$$

$$\left. \right\}.$$

- On the Figure (34), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (13). 564
565

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. 566
 Assume SuperHyperPart $\{V_i\}_{i=1}^7$ and non-SuperHyperPart $\{V_i\}_{i=7}^{12}$. Consider a 567
 Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $A_s = \{V_i\}_{i=1-7,9,11}$. Then A_s is called Neutrosophic 568
 SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION if the following expressions, terms 569
 and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION criteria 570
 holds.

$$\left| \left(\sum_{V_i \in A_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} F(V_i) \right) \right|$$

Table 13. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_5	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)
V_6	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	V_7	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)

Table 14. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_5	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)
V_6	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	V_7	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)

$$= \min_{B_s \subseteq V_{NSHG}} \left| \left\{ \left(\sum_{V_i \in B_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} F(V_i) \right) \right\} \right|$$

It's a dominating set and,

$$|N[v] \cap B_s| \geq 2, \text{ for every } v \in V.$$

}|.

- On the Figure (35), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (14). 571
572

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. 573

Assume SuperHyperPart $\{V_i\}_{i=1}^7$ and non-SuperHyperPart $\{V_i\}_{i=8}^{12}$. Consider a 574

Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $A_s = \{V_i\}_{i=1-12}$. Then A_s is called Neutrosophic 575

SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION if the following expressions, terms and 576

statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION criteria holds. 577

$$\left| \left(\sum_{V_i \in A_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} F(V_i) \right) \right|$$

$$= \min_{B_s \subseteq V_{NSHG}} \left| \left\{ \left(\sum_{V_i \in B_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} F(V_i) \right) \right\} \right|$$

It's a dominating set and,

$$|N[v] \cap B_s| \geq 2, \text{ for every } v \in V.$$

}|.

Example 4.3. Assume a Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle (SHG) S is a pair $S = (V, E)$ in the mentioned Neutrosophic Figures in every Neutrosophic items. 578
579

- On the Figure (36), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (15). 580
581

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume 582

SuperHyperExternal $\{V_i\}_{i=1}^7$ and non-SuperHyperInternal $\{V_i\}_{i=8}^{34}$. Consider a 583

Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $A_s = \{V_i\}_{i=1-7}$. Then A_s is called Neutrosophic 584

SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION if the following expressions, terms and 585

Table 15. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	$E_{i=37}$	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_5	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_6	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_7	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)

Table 16. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	$E_{i=37}$	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_5	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_6	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_7	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)

statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION criteria holds. 586

$$\begin{aligned}
 & |(\sum_{V_i \in A_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} F(V_i))| \\
 &= \min_{B_s \subseteq V_{NSHG}} |(\sum_{V_i \in B_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} F(V_i))| \\
 &\text{It's a dominating set and,} \\
 &|N[v] \cap B_s| \geq 2, \text{ for every } v \in V. \\
 & \} |.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (37), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (16). 587 588

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume SuperHyperExternal $\{V_i\}_{i=1}^7$ and non-SuperHyperInternal $\{V_i\}_{i=8}^{34}$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $A_s = \{V_i\}_{i=1-8,11,15,19,24-25,32-34}$. Then A_s is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION if the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION criteria holds. 589 590 591 592 593 594

$$\begin{aligned}
 & |(\sum_{V_i \in A_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} F(V_i))| \\
 &= \min_{B_s \subseteq V_{NSHG}} |(\sum_{V_i \in B_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} F(V_i))| \\
 &\text{It's a dominating set and,} \\
 &|N[v] \cap B_s| \geq 2, \text{ for every } v \in V. \\
 & \} |.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (38), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (17). 595 596

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume SuperHyperExternal $\{V_i\}_{i=1}^7$ and non-SuperHyperInternal $\{V_i\}_{i=8}^{34}$. Consider a 597 598

Table 17. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	$E_{i=37}$	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	V_5	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_6	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	V_7	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)

Table 18. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	$E_{i=37}$	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	V_5	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_6	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	V_7	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)

Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $A_s = \{V_i\}_{i=1-16,19,24-25,31-34}$. Then A_s is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION if the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION criteria holds.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & |(\sum_{V_i \in A_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} F(V_i))| \\
 & = \min_{B_s \subseteq V_{NSHG}} |(\sum_{V_i \in B_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} F(V_i))| \\
 & \text{It's a dominating set and,} \\
 & |N[v] \cap B_s| \geq 2, \text{ for every } v \in V. \\
 & \}.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (39), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (18).

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume SuperHyperExternal $\{V_i\}_{i=1}^7$ and non-SuperHyperInternal $\{V_i\}_{i=8}^{34}$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $A_s = \{V_i\}_{i=1-26,31-34}$. Then A_s is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION if the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION criteria holds.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & |(\sum_{V_i \in A_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} F(V_i))| \\
 & = \min_{B_s \subseteq V_{NSHG}} |(\sum_{V_i \in B_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} F(V_i))| \\
 & \text{It's a dominating set and,} \\
 & |N[v] \cap B_s| \geq 2, \text{ for every } v \in V. \\
 & \}.
 \end{aligned}$$

- On the Figure (40), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (19).

Table 19. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	$E_{i=37}$	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	V_5	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_6	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	V_7	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)

Table 20. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	$E_{i=37}$	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	V_5	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)
V_6	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	V_7	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume SuperHyperExternal $\{V_i\}_{i=1}^7$ and non-SuperHyperInternal $\{V_i\}_{i=8}^{34}$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $A_s = \{V_i\}_{i=1-34}$. Then A_s is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION if the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION criteria holds.

$$|(\sum_{V_i \in A_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} F(V_i))|$$

$$= \min_{B_s \subseteq V_{NSHG}} |(\sum_{V_i \in B_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} F(V_i))|$$

It's a dominating set and,

$$|N[v] \cap B_s| \geq 2, \text{ for every } v \in V.$$

}|.

- On the Figure (41), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (20).

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume SuperHyperExternal $\{V_i\}_{i=1}^7$ and non-SuperHyperInternal $\{V_i\}_{i=8}^{34}$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $A_s = \{V_i\}_{i=1-34}$. Then A_s is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION if the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION criteria holds.

$$|(\sum_{V_i \in A_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} F(V_i))|$$

$$= \min_{B_s \subseteq V_{NSHG}} |(\sum_{V_i \in B_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} F(V_i))|$$

It's a dominating set and,

$$|N[v] \cap B_s| \geq 2, \text{ for every } v \in V.$$

}|.

- On the Figure (42), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperNotion, namely, Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle (SHG), is up in the illustration of the Table (21).

Table 21. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle

V_i	$(T_{V_i}, I_{V_i}, F_{V_i})$	E_i	$(T_{E_i}, I_{E_i}, F_{E_i})$
V_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)	E_1	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_2	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	E_2	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_3	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	$E_{i=37}$	(0.26, 0.26, 0.26)
V_4	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	V_5	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)
V_6	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)	V_7	(0.24, 0.24, 0.24)

Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume SuperHyperExternal $\{V_i\}_{i=1}^7$ and non-SuperHyperInternal $\{V_i\}_{i=8}^{34}$. Consider a Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet $A_s = \{V_i\}_{i=1-34}$. Then A_s is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION if the following expressions, terms and statements is called Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION criteria holds.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & |(\sum_{V_i \in A_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in A_s} F(V_i))| \\
 &= \min_{B_s \subseteq V_{NSHG}} |(\sum_{V_i \in B_s} T(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} I(V_i), \sum_{V_i \in B_s} F(V_i))| \\
 &\text{It's a dominating set and,} \\
 &|N[v] \cap B_s| \geq 2, \text{ for every } v \in V. \\
 &\}.
 \end{aligned}$$

5 Main Result

Theorem 5.1. (Main Result and Main Theorem).

Assume every Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite has the letter z . The notion on the Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite and Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle don't coincide.

Proof.

(i). Let

$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &V_1^{P_i}, E_1, \\
 &V_1^{P_j}, E_2
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &P : \\
 &V_1^{P_i}, E_1, \\
 &V_1^{P_j}, E_2
 \end{aligned}$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned}
 &V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\
 &\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\
 &\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.
 \end{aligned}$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION. The latter is straightforward.

(ii). Let

$$P : \\ V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i^*, \\ V_{i+1}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{i+1}^*$$

$$P : \\ V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i^*, \\ V_{i+1}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{i+1}^*$$

is a longest SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $ESHG : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION could be applied. The unique embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION proposes some longest Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Proposition 5.2. *Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite ESHM be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume every Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex has the letter z . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION set is as follows.*

$$\{V_1^{P_i}, V_2^{P_i}\}, V_3^{P_i}, \dots, V_{|P_i|}^{P_i}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{P_i}, E_1, \\ V_1^{P_j}, E_2$$

$$P : \\ V_1^{P_i}, E_1, \\ V_1^{P_j}, E_2$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Proposition 5.3. *Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite ESHM be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume every Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex has the letter z . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION number is as follows.*

$$|P_i| \times 0.26.$$

Proof. Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{P_i}, E_1, \\ V_1^{P_j}, E_2$$

$$P : \\ V_1^{P_i}, E_1, \\ V_1^{P_j}, E_2$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite ESHM : (V, E) . There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Proposition 5.4. *Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle (ESHC) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume every Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex has the letter z . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION set is as follows.*

$$\{ \\ V_i^{INTERNAL}, \\ V_{i+1}^{INTERNAL}, \dots \\ V_{|E_i|}^{INTERNAL} \\ \}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : \\ V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i^*, \\ V_{i+1}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{i+1}^*$$

$$P : \\ V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i^*, \\ V_{i+1}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{i+1}^*$$

is a longest SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle ESHC : (V, E) . There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv$$

$$\begin{aligned} \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION. The latter is straightforward. Then there’s at least one Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION. Thus the notion of quasi isn’t up and the SuperHyperNotions based on Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION could be applied. The unique embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION proposes some longest Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Proposition 5.5. *Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle (ESHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume every Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertex has the letter z . The Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION number is as follows.*

$$|E_i| \times 0.26.$$

Proof. Let

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i^*, \\ V_{i+1}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{i+1}^* \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i^*, \\ V_{i+1}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{i+1}^* \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $ESHG : (V, E)$. There’s a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION. The latter is straightforward. Then there’s at least one Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION. Thus the notion of quasi isn’t up and the SuperHyperNotions based on Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION could be applied. The unique embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION proposes some longest Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Definition 5.6. (Uniform Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite and Uniform Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle).

- (i). Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Every pair of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices has the same maximum letter, i.e., Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices mutually has the same maximum letter. A Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$ is called **Uniform Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite**.

(ii). Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Every pair of Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices has the same maximum letter, i.e., Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices mutually has the same maximum letter. A Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$ is called **Uniform Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle**.

Proposition 5.7. *Let an Uniform Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite ESHM be a pair $S = (V, E)$. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION set is as follows.*

$$\{V_1^{P_i}, V_2^{P_i}\}, V_3^{P_i}, \dots, V_{|P_i|}^{P_i}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{P_i}, E_1, \\ V_1^{P_j}, E_2$$

$$P : \\ V_1^{P_i}, E_1, \\ V_1^{P_j}, E_2$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite ESHM : (V, E) . There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Proposition 5.8. *Let an Uniform Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite ESHM be a pair $S = (V, E)$. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION number is as follows.*

$$|P_i| \times 0.26.$$

Proof. Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{P_i}, E_1, \\ V_1^{P_j}, E_2$$

$$P : \\ V_1^{P_i}, E_1, \\ V_1^{P_j}, E_2$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite ESHM : (V, E) . There's a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv$$

$$\begin{aligned} \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Proposition 5.9. *Let an Uniform Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle (ESHC) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION set is as follows.*

$$\left\{ \begin{aligned} &V_i^{INTERNAL}, \\ &V_{i+1}^{INTERNAL}, \dots \\ &V_{|E_i|}^{INTERNAL} \end{aligned} \right\}$$

Proof. Let

$$P : \begin{aligned} &V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i^*, \\ &V_{i+1}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{i+1}^* \end{aligned}$$

$$P : \begin{aligned} &V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i^*, \\ &V_{i+1}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{i+1}^* \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $ESHC : (V, E)$. There’s a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION. The latter is straightforward. Then there’s at least one Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION. Thus the notion of quasi isn’t up and the SuperHyperNotions based on Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION could be applied. The unique embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION proposes some longest Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Proposition 5.10. *Let an Uniform Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle (ESHC) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. The Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION number is as follows.*

$$|E_i| \times 0.26.$$

Proof. Let

$$P : V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i^*,$$

$$V_{i+1}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{i+1}^*$$

741

$$P : \\ V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i^*, \\ V_{i+1}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{i+1}^*$$

is a longest SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $ESH C : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

742

743

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term "EXTERNAL" implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION could be applied. The unique embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION proposes some longest Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

744

745

746

747

748

749

750

751

Proposition 5.11. (Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite and Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle).

752

753

- (i). Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume two Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices, from different SuperHyperParts, have the maximum letter. Then the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices don't have the same maximum letter, are in every Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION set.
- (ii). Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Assume every Neutrosophic EXTERNAL SuperHyperVertices with distance two have the maximum letter. Then the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices don't have the same maximum letter, are in every Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION set.

754

755

756

757

758

759

760

761

Proof.

762

(i). Let

763

$$P : \\ V_1^{P_i}, E_1, \\ V_1^{P_j}, E_2$$

764

$$P : \\ V_1^{P_i}, E_1, \\ V_1^{P_j}, E_2$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESH M : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

765

766

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv$$

$$\exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION. The latter is straightforward.

(ii). Let

$$P : \\ V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i^*, \\ V_{i+1}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{i+1}^*$$

$$P : \\ V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i^*, \\ V_{i+1}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{i+1}^*$$

is a longest SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $ESHG : (V, E)$. There’s a new way to redefine as

$$V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z \equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z.$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION. The latter is straightforward. Then there’s at least one Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION. Thus the notion of quasi isn’t up and the SuperHyperNotions based on Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION could be applied. The unique embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION proposes some longest Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

Proposition 5.12. (*Embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar and Embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyperStar*).

- (i). Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Then two Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices, from different SuperHyperParts, is in every Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION set.
- (ii). Let a Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle (SHG) S be a pair $S = (V, E)$. Then every Neutrosophic EXTERNAL SuperHyperVertices with distance two is in every Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION set.

Proof.

(i). Let

$$P : \\ V_1^{P_i}, E_1, \\ V_1^{P_j}, E_2$$

$$P : \\ V_1^{P_i}, E_1,$$

$$V_1^{P_j}, E_2$$

be a longest path taken a connected Extreme SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. & \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION. The latter is straightforward.

(ii). Let

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i^*, \\ V_{i+1}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{i+1}^* \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} P : \\ V_i^{EXTERNAL}, E_i^*, \\ V_{i+1}^{EXTERNAL}, E_{i+1}^* \end{aligned}$$

is a longest SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION taken from a connected Extreme SuperHyperCycle $ESHC : (V, E)$. There's a new way to redefine as

$$\begin{aligned} V_i^{EXTERNAL} \sim V_j^{EXTERNAL} &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL} \in E_z &\equiv \\ \exists! E_z \in E_{ESHG:(V,E)}, \{V_i^{EXTERNAL}, V_j^{EXTERNAL}\} \subseteq E_z. & \end{aligned}$$

The term “EXTERNAL” implies $|N(V_i^{EXTERNAL})| \geq |N(V_j)|$ where V_j is corresponded to $V_i^{EXTERNAL}$ in the literatures of Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION. The latter is straightforward. Then there's at least one Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION. Thus the notion of quasi isn't up and the SuperHyperNotions based on Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION could be applied. The unique embedded Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION proposes some longest Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION excerpt from some representatives. The latter is straightforward. $\square$

6 Neutrosophic Applications in Cancer's Neutrosophic Recognition

The cancer is the Neutrosophic disease but the Neutrosophic model is going to figure out what's going on this Neutrosophic phenomenon. The special Neutrosophic case of this Neutrosophic disease is considered and as the consequences of the model, some parameters are used. The cells are under attack of this disease but the moves of the cancer in the special region are the matter of mind. The Neutrosophic recognition of the cancer could help to find some Neutrosophic treatments for this Neutrosophic disease.

In the following, some Neutrosophic steps are Neutrosophic devised on this disease.

Step 1. (Neutrosophic Definition) The Neutrosophic recognition of the cancer in the long-term Neutrosophic function.

Table 22. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

Figure 44. a Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite Associated to the Notions of Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION

The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Neutrosophic Algorithm in previous Neutrosophic result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperBipartite $ESHB : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (43), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION.

8 Case 2: The Increasing Neutrosophic Steps Toward Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite as Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel

Step 4. (Neutrosophic Solution) In the Neutrosophic Figure (44), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite is Neutrosophic highlighted and Neutrosophic featured.

By using the Neutrosophic Figure (44) and the Table (23), the Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite is obtained.

The obtained Neutrosophic SuperHyperSet, by the Neutrosophic Algorithm in previous result, of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperVertices of the connected Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite $ESHM : (V, E)$, in the Neutrosophic SuperHyperModel (44), is the Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION.

Table 23. The Values of Vertices, SuperVertices, Edges, HyperEdges, and SuperHyperEdges Belong to The Neutrosophic SuperHyperMultipartite

The Values of The Vertices	The Number of Position in Alphabet
The Values of The SuperVertices	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The Edges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The HyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Vertices
The Values of The SuperHyperEdges	The maximum Values of Its Endpoints

9 Wondering Open Problems But As The Directions To Forming The Motivations

In what follows, some “problems” and some “questions” are proposed.

The SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION are defined on a real-world application, titled “Cancer’s Recognitions”.

Question 9.1. *Which the else SuperHyperModels could be defined based on Cancer’s recognitions?*

Question 9.2. *Are there some SuperHyperNotions related to SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION?*

Question 9.3. *Are there some Algorithms to be defined on the SuperHyperModels to compute them?*

Question 9.4. *Which the SuperHyperNotions are related to beyond the SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION?*

Problem 9.5. *The SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION and the Neutrosophic SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION do a SuperHyperModel for the Cancer’s recognitions and they’re based on SuperHyperDOUBLE DOMINATION, are there else?*

Problem 9.6. *Which the fundamental SuperHyperNumbers are related to these SuperHyperNumbers types-results?*

Problem 9.7. *What’s the independent research based on Cancer’s recognitions concerning the multiple types of SuperHyperNotions?*

10 Conclusion and Closing Remarks

In this section, closing and concluding remarks are presented. The drawbacks of this scientific research are shown. Some advantages and disadvantages of this scientific research are highlighted.

This scientific research uses some approaches to further understand the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs. In this effort, two SuperHyperNotions are defined on the DOUBLE DOMINATION. For this reason, in the second definition, the original definition of the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph is redefined on the position of the alphabets. Based on the new Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph definition, the new SuperHyperNotion, Neutrosophic DOUBLE DOMINATION, finds a suitable background to implement some results on. Some SuperHyperClasses and some Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses are the subjects of this scientific research on modeling areas that are subject to cancer attacks in order to recognize this disease as mentioned under the title “Cancer Diagnosis”. To formalize the SuperHyperNotion, DOUBLE DOMINATION, SuperHyperClasses and new SuperHyperClasses instances are introduced. Some general results are summarized in

the DOUBLE DOMINATION and Neutrosophic DOUBLE DOMINATION sections. Clarifications, examples, and literature reviews go all the way. In this scientific research, the literature review has met the lines containing concepts and results. SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph are super-hypermodels in “cancer diagnosis” and both are the foundation of the background of this scientific research. Sometimes cancer has occurred in an area full of cells, cell groups, and embedded styles. In this section, SuperHyperModel proposes SuperHyperNotions, formally called “DOUBLE DOMINATION”, based on the connections of Cancer’s movements in the longest and strongest styles with the formation of design and architecture, in terms of terms and whispering words. . The “SuperHyper” prefix refers to the topic of embedded styles to explore the background of SuperHyperNotions. In

Table 24. A look at this scientific research and beyond

Advantages	Limitations
1. Redefining the Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph	1. General Results
2. DOUBLE DOMINATION	
3. Neutrosophic DOUBLE DOMINATION	2. Other SuperHyperNumbers
4. modeling cancer diagnoses	
5. SuperHyperClasses	3. SuperHyperFamilies

the table (24), the advantages and ways of this scientific research are specified, pointed out and expressed.

11 Background

There are some scientific researches covering the topic of this scientific research. In what follows, there are some discussion and literature reviews about them.

The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph As Hyper Tool On Super Toot*” in **Ref. [1]** by Henry Garrett (2023). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on general forms with introducing used neutrosophic classes of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It’s published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled “*Current Trends in Mass Communication (CTMC)*” with ISO abbreviation “*Curr Trends Mass Comm*” in volume 2 and issue 1 with pages 32-55.

The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled “*Some Super Hyper Degrees and Co-Super Hyper Degrees on Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graphs And Super Hyper Graphs Alongside Applications in Cancer’s Treatments*” in **Ref. [2]** by Henry Garrett (2023). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on fundamental notions and using vital tools in Cancer’s Treatments. It’s published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled “*Journal of Mathematical Techniques and Computational Mathematics(JMTCM)*” with ISO abbreviation “*J Math Techniques Comput Math*” in volume 2 and issue 1 with pages 35-47. The research article studies deeply with choosing directly neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph and SuperHyperGraph. It’s the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background and fundamental SuperHyperNumbers.

The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled “*A Research on Cancer’s Recognition and Neutrosophic Super Hypergraph by Eulerian Super Hyper Cycles and Hamiltonian Sets as Hyper Covering Versus Super separations*” in **Ref. [3]** by Henry Garrett (2023). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on fundamental notions and using vital tools in Cancer’s Recognition. It’s published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled “*Journal of Mathematical Techniques and Computational Mathematics(JMTCM)*” with ISO abbreviation “*J Math Techniques Comput Math*” in volume 2 and issue 3 with pages 136-148. The research article studies deeply with choosing directly neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph and SuperHyperGraph. It’s the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background and fundamental SuperHyperNumbers.

The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled “*Neutrosophic 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in the SuperHyperFunction to Use Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Beyond*” in **Ref. [4]** by Henry Garrett (2023). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on fundamental SuperHyperNumber and using neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It’s published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled “*Journal of Mathematical Techniques and Computational Mathematics(JMTCM)*” with ISO abbreviation “*J Math Techniques Comput Math*” in volume 2 and issue 6 with pages 221-307. The research article studies deeply with choosing directly neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph and SuperHyperGraph. It’s the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background and fundamental SuperHyperNumbers. The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled “*New Ideas in Recognition of Cancer and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph by Initial Eulerian-Path-Cut as Hyper Initial Eulogy on Super Initial EULA*” in **Ref. [5]** by Henry Garrett (2023). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on fundamental SuperHyperNumber and using neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It’s published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled “*International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics Research*” with ISO abbreviation “*IJPAMR*” in volume 3 and issue 2 with pages 60-88 and doi: 10.51483/IJPAMR.3.2.2023.60-88. The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled “*New Ideas in Recognition of Cancer and Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graph by Eulerian-Path-Cut as Hyper Eulogy-Path-Cut on Super EULA-Path-Cut*” in **Ref. [6]** by Henry Garrett (2023). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on fundamental SuperHyperNumber and using neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It’s published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled “*International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics Research*” with ISO abbreviation “*IJPAMR*” in volume 3 and issue 2 with pages 102-124 and doi: 10.51483/IJPAMR.3.2.2023.102-124. The research article studies deeply with choosing directly neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph and SuperHyperGraph. It’s the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background and fundamental SuperHyperNumbers. The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled “*Super Hyper Dominating and Super Hyper Resolving on Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graphs and Their Directions in Game Theory and Neutrosophic Super Hyper Classes*” in **Ref. [7]** by Henry Garrett (2022). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on fundamental SuperHyperNumber and using neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It’s published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled “*Journal of Mathematical Techniques and Computational Mathematics(JMTCM)*” with ISO abbreviation “*J Math Techniques Comput Math*” in volume 1 and issue 3 with pages

242-263. The research article studies deeply with choosing directly neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph and SuperHyperGraph. It's the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background and fundamental SuperHyperNumbers. The seminal paper and groundbreaking article is titled "*neutrosophic co-degree and neutrosophic degree alongside chromatic numbers in the setting of some classes related to neutrosophic hypergraphs*" in **Ref. [8]** by Henry Garrett (2023). In this research article, a novel approach is implemented on SuperHyperGraph and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph based on general forms without using neutrosophic classes of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It's published in prestigious and fancy journal is entitled "*Journal of Current Trends in Computer Science Research (JCTCSR)*" with ISO abbreviation "*J Curr Trends Comp Sci Res*" in volume 2 and issue 1 with pages 16-24. The research article studies deeply with choosing neutrosophic hypergraphs instead of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It's the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background. The research article studies deeply with choosing neutrosophic hypergraphs instead of neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph. It's the breakthrough toward independent results based on initial background. In some articles are titled "*0039 — Closing Numbers and Super-Closing Numbers as (Dual)Resolving and (Dual)Coloring alongside (Dual)Dominating in (Neutrosophic)n-SuperHyperGraph*" in **Ref. [9]** by Henry Garrett (2022), "*0049 — (Failed)1-Zero-Forcing Number in Neutrosophic Graphs*" in **Ref. [10]** by Henry Garrett (2022), "*Extreme SuperHyperClique as the Firm Scheme of Confrontation under Cancer's Recognition as the Model in The Setting of (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*" in **Ref. [11]** by Henry Garrett (2022), "*Uncertainty On The Act And Effect Of Cancer Alongside The Foggy Positions Of Cells Toward Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperClique inside Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Titled Cancer's Recognition*" in **Ref. [12]** by Henry Garrett (2022), "*Neutrosophic Version Of Separates Groups Of Cells In Cancer's Recognition On Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*" in **Ref. [13]** by Henry Garrett (2022), "*The Shift Paradigm To Classify Separately The Cells and Affected Cells Toward The Totality Under Cancer's Recognition By New Multiple Definitions On the Sets Polynomials Alongside Numbers In The (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperMatching Theory Based on SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph*" in **Ref. [14]** by Henry Garrett (2022), "*Breaking the Continuity and Uniformity of Cancer In The Worst Case of Full Connections With Extreme Failed SuperHyperClique In Cancer's Recognition Applied in (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*" in **Ref. [15]** by Henry Garrett (2022), "*Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperStable as the Survivors on the Cancer's Neutrosophic Recognition Based on Uncertainty to All Modes in Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*" in **Ref. [16]** by Henry Garrett (2022), "*Extremism of the Attacked Body Under the Cancer's Circumstances Where Cancer's Recognition Titled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*" in **Ref. [17]** by Henry Garrett (2022), "*(Neutrosophic) 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in Cancer's Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*" in **Ref. [18]** by Henry Garrett (2022), "*Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer's Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints*" in **Ref. [19]** by Henry Garrett (2022), "*Neutrosophic 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in the SuperHyperFunction To Use Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs on Cancer's Neutrosophic Recognition And Beyond*" in **Ref. [20]** by Henry Garrett (2022), "*(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperStable on Cancer's Recognition by Well- SuperHyperModelled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*" in **Ref. [21]** by Henry Garrett (2022), "*Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer's Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints*" in **Ref. [17]** by Henry Garrett (2022), "*Basic Notions on (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperForcing And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling in Cancer's Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*" in **Ref. [22]** by Henry Garrett (2022), "*Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer's Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints*"

in Ref. [23] by Henry Garrett (2022), “(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions Featuring (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperAlliances” in Ref. [24] by Henry Garrett (2022), “(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperAlliances With SuperHyperDefensive and SuperHyperOffensive Type-SuperHyperSet On (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions And Related (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperClasses” in Ref. [25] by Henry Garrett (2022), “SuperHyperGirth on SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions” in Ref. [26] by Henry Garrett (2022), “Some SuperHyperDegrees and Co-SuperHyperDegrees on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs and SuperHyperGraphs Alongside Applications in Cancer’s Treatments” in Ref. [27] by Henry Garrett (2022), “SuperHyperDominating and SuperHyperResolving on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs And Their Directions in Game Theory and Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses” in Ref. [28] by Henry Garrett (2022), “SuperHyperMatching By (R-)Definitions And Polynomials To Monitor Cancer’s Recognition In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs” in Ref. [300] by Henry Garrett (2023), “The Focus on The Partitions Obtained By Parallel Moves In The Cancer’s Extreme Recognition With Different Types of Extreme SuperHyperMatching Set and Polynomial on (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in Ref. [301] by Henry Garrett (2023), “Extreme Failed SuperHyperClique Decides the Failures on the Cancer’s Recognition in the Perfect Connections of Cancer’s Attacks By SuperHyperModels Named (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in Ref. [302] by Henry Garrett (2023), “Indeterminacy On The All Possible Connections of Cells In Front of Cancer’s Attacks In The Terms of Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperClique on Cancer’s Recognition called Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs” in Ref. [303] by Henry Garrett (2023), “Perfect Directions Toward Idealism in Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition Forwarding Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs” in Ref. [306] by Henry Garrett (2023), “Demonstrating Complete Connections in Every Embedded Regions and Sub-Regions in the Terms of Cancer’s Recognition and (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperClique” in Ref. [307] by Henry Garrett (2023), “Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic Regions titled neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperStable in Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition modeled in the Form of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs” in Ref. [310] by Henry Garrett (2023), “Using the Tool As (Neutrosophic) Failed SuperHyperStable To SuperHyperModel Cancer’s Recognition Titled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in Ref. [313] by Henry Garrett (2023), “Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints” in Ref. [314] by Henry Garrett (2023), “(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperStable on Cancer’s Recognition by Well-SuperHyperModelled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in Ref. [315] by Henry Garrett (2023), “Neutrosophic 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in the SuperHyperFunction To Use Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition And Beyond” in Ref. [316] by Henry Garrett (2022), “(Neutrosophic) 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in Ref. [317] by Henry Garrett (2022), “Basic Notions on (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperForcing And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs” in Ref. [318] by Henry Garrett (2022), “Basic Neutrosophic Notions Concerning SuperHyperDominating and Neutrosophic SuperHyperResolving in SuperHyperGraph” in Ref. [329] by Henry Garrett (2022), “Initial Material of Neutrosophic Preliminaries to Study Some Neutrosophic Notions Based on Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) in Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)” in Ref. [330] by Henry Garrett (2022), and [4–330], there are some endeavors to formalize the basic SuperHyperNotions about neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph and SuperHyperGraph alongside scientific research books at [331–491]. Two popular scientific research books in Scribd in the terms of high

readers, 5679 and 6667 respectively, on neutrosophic science is on [492, 493].

Some scientific studies and scientific researches about neutrosophic graphs, are proposed as book in **Ref.** [492] by Henry Garrett (2023) which is indexed by Google Scholar and has more than 5679 readers in Scribd. It's titled "*Beyond Neutrosophic Graphs*" and published by Dr. Henry Garrett. This research book covers different types of notions and settings in neutrosophic graph theory and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph theory.

Also, some scientific studies and scientific researches about neutrosophic graphs, are proposed as book in **Ref.** [493] by Henry Garrett (2023) which is indexed by Google Scholar and has more than 6667 readers in Scribd. It's titled "*Neutrosophic Duality*" and published by Dr. Henry Garrett. This research book presents different types of notions SuperHyperResolving and SuperHyperDominating in the setting of duality in neutrosophic graph theory and neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph theory. This research book has scrutiny on the complement of the intended set and the intended set, simultaneously. It's smart to consider a set but acting on its complement that what's done in this research book which is popular in the terms of high readers in Scribd.

See the seminal scientific researches [1-3]. The formalization of the notions on the framework of notions in SuperHyperGraphs, Neutrosophic notions in SuperHyperGraphs theory, and (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs theory at [4-330] alongside scientific research books at [331-491]. Two popular scientific research books in Scribd, in the terms of high readers, 5679 and 6667 respectively, on neutrosophic science is on [492, 493].

References

1. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph As Hyper Tool On Super Toot", *Curr Trends Mass Comm* 2(1) (2023) 32-55. (doi: 10.33140/CTMC.02.01.03).
2. Henry Garrett, "*Some Super Hyper Degrees and Co-Super Hyper Degrees on Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graphs And Super Hyper Graphs Alongside Applications in Cancer's Treatments*", *J Math Techniques Comput Math* 2(1) (2023) 35-47. (doi: 10.33140/JMTCM.02.01.05).
3. Henry Garrett, "*A Research on Cancer's Recognition and Neutrosophic Super Hypergraph by Eulerian Super Hyper Cycles and Hamiltonian Sets as Hyper Covering Versus Super separations*", *J Math Techniques Comput Math* 2(3) (2023) 136-148. (doi: 10.33140/JMTCM.02.03.03).
4. Henry Garrett, "*Neutrosophic 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in the SuperHyperFunction to Use Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs on Cancer's Neutrosophic Recognition and Beyond*", *J Math Techniques Comput Math* 2(6) (2023) 221-307. (doi: 10.33140/JMTCM.02.06.04).
5. Henry Garrett, "*New Ideas in Recognition of Cancer and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph by Initial Eulerian-Path-Cut as Hyper Initial Eulogy on Super Initial EULA*", *International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics Research* 3(2) (2023) 60-88. (doi: 10.51483/IJPAMR.3.2.2023.60-88).
6. Henry Garrett, "*New Ideas in Recognition of Cancer and Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graph by Eulerian-Path-Cut as Hyper Eulogy-Path-Cut on Super EULA-Path-Cut*", *International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics Research* 3(2) (2023) 102-124. (doi: 10.51483/IJPAMR.3.2.2023.102-124).

7. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas in Recognition of Cancer and Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graph by Eulerian-Path-Cut as Hyper Eulogy-Path-Cut on Super EULA-Path-Cut*”, J Curr Trends Comp Sci Res 2(1) (2023) 16-24. (doi: 10.33140/JCTCSR.02.01.04) 1114
1115
1116
1117
8. Henry Garrett, “*Super Hyper Dominating and Super Hyper Resolving on Neutrosophic Super Hyper Graphs and Their Directions in Game Theory and Neutrosophic Super Hyper Classes*”, J Math Techniques Comput Math 1(3) (2022) 242-263. (doi: 10.33140/JMTCM.01.03.09) 1118
1119
1120
1121
9. Garrett, Henry. “*0039 — Closing Numbers and Super-Closing Numbers as (Dual)Resolving and (Dual)Coloring alongside (Dual)Dominating in (Neutrosophic)n-SuperHyperGraph.*” CERN European Organization for Nuclear Research - Zenodo, Nov. 2022. CERN European Organization for Nuclear Research, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6319942>. <https://oa.mg/work/10.5281/zenodo.6319942> 1122
1123
1124
1125
1126
1127
10. Garrett, Henry. “*0049 — (Failed)1-Zero-Forcing Number in Neutrosophic Graphs.*” CERN European Organization for Nuclear Research - Zenodo, Feb. 2022. CERN European Organization for Nuclear Research, <https://doi.org/10.13140/rg.2.2.35241.26724>. <https://oa.mg/work/10.13140/rg.2.2.35241.26724> 1128
1129
1130
1131
1132
11. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperClique as the Firm Scheme of Confrontation under Cancer’s Recognition as the Model in The Setting of (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010308 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0308.v1). 1133
1134
1135
1136
12. Henry Garrett, “*Uncertainty On The Act And Effect Of Cancer Alongside The Foggy Positions Of Cells Toward Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperClique inside Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Titled Cancer’s Recognition*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010282 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0282.v1). 1137
1138
1139
1140
13. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Version Of Separates Groups Of Cells In Cancer’s Recognition On Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010267 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0267.v1). 1141
1142
1143
14. Henry Garrett, “*The Shift Paradigm To Classify Separately The Cells and Affected Cells Toward The Totality Under Cancer’s Recognition By New Multiple Definitions On the Sets Polynomials Alongside Numbers In The (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperMatching Theory Based on SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010265 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0265.v1). 1144
1145
1146
1147
1148
1149
15. Henry Garrett, “*Breaking the Continuity and Uniformity of Cancer In The Worst Case of Full Connections With Extreme Failed SuperHyperClique In Cancer’s Recognition Applied in (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010262,(doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0262.v1). 1150
1151
1152
1153
16. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperStable as the Survivors on the Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition Based on Uncertainty to All Modes in Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010240 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0240.v1). 1154
1155
1156
1157
17. Henry Garrett, “*Extremism of the Attacked Body Under the Cancer’s Circumstances Where Cancer’s Recognition Titled (Neutrosophic)* 1158
1159

- SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010224, (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0224.v1). 1160
1161
18. Henry Garrett, “(Neutrosophic) 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs”, Preprints 2023, 2023010105 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0105.v1). 1162
1163
1164
19. Henry Garrett, “Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints”, Preprints 2023, 2023010088 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0088.v1). 1165
1166
1167
1168
20. Henry Garrett, “Neutrosophic 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in the SuperHyperFunction To Use Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition And Beyond”, Preprints 2023, 2023010044 1169
1170
1171
21. Henry Garrett, “(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperStable on Cancer’s Recognition by Well- SuperHyperModelled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs”, Preprints 2023, 2023010043 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0043.v1). 1172
1173
1174
22. Henry Garrett, “Basic Notions on (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperForcing And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs”, Preprints 2023, 2023010105 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0105.v1). 1175
1176
1177
1178
23. Henry Garrett, “Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints”, Preprints 2023, 2023010088 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0088.v1). 1179
1180
1181
1182
24. Henry Garrett, “(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions Featuring (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperAlliances”, Preprints 2022, 2022120549 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0549.v1). 1183
1184
1185
25. Henry Garrett, “(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperAlliances With SuperHyperDefensive and SuperHyperOffensive Type-SuperHyperSet On (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions And Related (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperClasses”, Preprints 2022, 2022120540 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0540.v1). 1186
1187
1188
1189
1190
26. Henry Garrett, “SuperHyperGirth on SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions”, Preprints 2022, 2022120500 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0500.v1). 1191
1192
1193
27. Henry Garrett, “Some SuperHyperDegrees and Co-SuperHyperDegrees on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs and SuperHyperGraphs Alongside Applications in Cancer’s Treatments”, Preprints 2022, 2022120324 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0324.v1). 1194
1195
1196
1197
28. Henry Garrett, “SuperHyperDominating and SuperHyperResolving on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs And Their Directions in Game Theory and Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses”, Preprints 2022, 2022110576 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202211.0576.v1). 1198
1199
1200
1201
29. Henry Garrett, “Star and Wheel on Recognition of Cancer and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph with a Specific Type of Independency of SuperHyperVertices”, Preprints 2024, , 2024020663 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202402.0663.v1). 1202
1203
1204
1205

30. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By PAIRED-DOMINATION", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14577030). 1206
1207
1208
31. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By PAIRED-DOMINATION", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14568932). 1209
1210
1211
32. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By PAIRED-DOMINATION", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14566069). 1212
1213
1214
33. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14562607). 1215
1216
1217
1218
34. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14558506). 1219
1220
1221
1222
35. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14555481). 1223
1224
1225
1226
36. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By DOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14552432). 1227
1228
1229
37. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By STRONGLY-DOMINATING SET", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14547873). 1230
1231
1232
38. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By STRONGLY-DOMINATING SET", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14543895). 1233
1234
1235
1236
39. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By DOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14540759). 1237
1238
1239
40. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By DOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14536608). 1240
1241
1242
41. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By DOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14527040). 1243
1244
1245
42. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By ESTRAINED DOMINATION", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14515147). 1246
1247
1248

43. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By ESTRAINED DOMINATION", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14507321). 1249-1251
44. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By RESTRAINED DOMINATION", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14501230). 1252-1254
45. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Dom-forcing", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14477108). 1255-1257
46. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Dom-forcing", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14449513). 1258-1260
47. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Dom-forcing", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14261015). 1261-1263
48. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Diamond search Edge", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14031032). 1264-1266
49. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Diamond search Edge", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14019047). 1267-1269
50. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Diamond search Edge", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13957693). 1270-1272
51. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Triangle-free search Edge", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13909326). 1273-1275
52. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Triangle-free search Edge", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13893734). 1276-1278
53. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Triangle-free search Edge", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13890872). 1279-1281
54. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Diamond search", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13834065). 1282-1284
55. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Diamond search", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13826744). 1285-1287
56. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Diamond search", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13823150). 1288-1290
57. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Triangle-free search", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13748678). 1291-1293

58. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Triangle-free search", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13629264). 1294
1295
1296
59. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Triangle-free search", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13618512). 1297
1298
1299
60. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Edge Cover", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13457634). 1300
1301
1302
61. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Edge Cover", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13447621). 1303
1304
1305
62. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Edge Cover", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13386125). 1306
1307
1308
63. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Vertex Cover", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13359880). 1309
1310
1311
64. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Vertex Cover", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13359103). 1312
1313
1314
65. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Vertex Cover", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13329472). 1315
1316
1317
66. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Burning Number From Graph Searching", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13091499). 1318
1319
1320
67. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Burning Number From Graph Searching", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13134329). 1321
1322
1323
68. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Burning Number From Graph Searching", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13218489). 1324
1325
1326
69. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Zero Forcing From Graph Searching", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12788786). 1327
1328
1329
70. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Zero Forcing", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12752339). 1330
1331
1332
71. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Zero Forcing", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12738172). 1333
1334
1335
72. Henry Garrett, "New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Connected Perfect Dual Domination", Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12680424). 1336
1337
1338

73. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Connected Perfect Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12675758). 1339
1340
1341
74. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Connected Perfect Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12656919). 1342
1343
1344
75. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Stable Perfect Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12576337). 1345
1346
1347
76. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Stable Perfect Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12556338). 1348
1349
1350
77. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Stable Perfect Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12536399). 1351
1352
1353
78. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Perfect Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12174846). 1354
1355
1356
79. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Perfect Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12129978). 1357
1358
1359
80. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Perfect Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12024191). 1360
1361
1362
81. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Connected Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11661528). 1363
1364
1365
82. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Connected Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11651866). 1366
1367
1368
83. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Connected Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11634496). 1369
1370
1371
84. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Stable Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11513482). 1372
1373
1374
85. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Stable Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11479559). 1375
1376
1377
86. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Stable Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11438586). 1378
1379
1380
87. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Simple Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11253553). 1381
1382
1383

88. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Simple Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11218489). 1384
1385
1386
89. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Simple Dual Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11169069). 1387
1388
1389
90. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Stable Perfect Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11075522). 1390
1391
1392
91. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Stable Perfect Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10982844). 1393
1394
1395
92. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Stable Perfect Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10963312). 1396
1397
1398
93. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Total Perfect Domination”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10929590). 1399
1400
1401
94. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Total Perfect Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10918770). 1402
1403
1404
95. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Total Perfect Domination”, Zenodo 2024, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10910154). 1405
1406
1407
96. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Perfect Domination”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10899659). 1408
1409
1410
97. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Perfect Domination”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10895887). 1411
1412
1413
98. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Perfect Domination”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10888691). 1414
1415
1416
99. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Counterproposal Star and Counteroffer Wheel By Counterargument Stable Sequence As Hyper Findings On Super Gatherings”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10851065). 1417
1418
1419
1420
100. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Counterproposal Bipartite and Counteroffer Path By Counterargument Stable Sequence As Hyper Findings On Super Gatherings”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10796076). 1421
1422
1423
1424
101. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Counterproposal Multipartite and Counteroffer Cycle By Counterargument Stable Sequence As Hyper Findings On Super Gatherings”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10640905). 1425
1426
1427
1428

102. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Strongly Resolving Sequence As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.17389.97769). 1429
1430
1431
1432
103. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Strongly Resolving Sequence As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.28685.10727). 1433
1434
1435
1436
104. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Strongly Resolving Sequence As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.24994.20169). 1437
1438
1439
1440
105. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By Dominating Sequence As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10371529). 1441
1442
1443
106. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By Dominating Sequence As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10299535). 1444
1445
1446
107. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By Dominating Sequence As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10263440). 1447
1448
1449
1450
108. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By STABLE As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10028600). 1451
1452
1453
109. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By STABLE As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8310454). 1454
1455
1456
110. Henry Garrett, “Recognition of Cancer With Bipartite and Path as Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By the Tool Called Stability”, Preprints 2023, 2023081972 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202308.1972.v1). 1457
1458
1459
111. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By STABLE As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8262182). 1460
1461
1462
112. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By REVERSE CONNECTIVE DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8206877). 1463
1464
1465
1466
113. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By REVERSE CONNECTIVE DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8206834). 1467
1468
1469
1470
114. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By REVERSE CONNECTIVE DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8206773). 1471
1472
1473
1474

115. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By EQUAL CONNECTIVE DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8201319). 1475
1476
1477
1478
116. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By EQUAL CONNECTIVE DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8201255). 1479
1480
1481
1482
117. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By EQUAL CONNECTIVE DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8201165). 1483
1484
1485
1486
118. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By CONNECTIVE DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8196147). 1487
1488
1489
1490
119. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By CONNECTIVE DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8196132). 1491
1492
1493
1494
120. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By CONNECTIVE DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8196099). 1495
1496
1497
1498
121. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Bipartite and Path By DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8187955). 1499
1500
1501
122. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Star and Wheel By DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8161878). 1502
1503
1504
123. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With Multipartite and Cycle By DOMINATION As Hyper Decoration On Super Density”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8176262). 1505
1506
1507
124. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperPerfect Search As Hyper Perf On Super Perfidy”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8104836). 1508
1509
1510
125. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Perfidy By Hyper Perf Of SuperHyperPerfect Search In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8104857). 1511
1512
1513
126. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Reverse Strict Dimension Dominating As Hyper Dimple On Super Dimity”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8092796). 1514
1515
1516
127. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Dimity By Hyper Dimple Of Reverse Strict Dimension Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8092766). 1517
1518
1519

128. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Unequal Dimension Dominating As Hyper Dimple On Super Dimity”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8088438). 1520
1521
1522
129. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Dimity By Hyper Dimple Of Unequal Dimension Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8088387). 1523
1524
1525
130. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Strict Dimension Dominating As Hyper Dimple On Super Dimity”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8084436). 1526
1527
1528
131. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Dimity By Hyper Dimple Of Strict Dimension Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8084420). 1529
1530
1531
132. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Reverse Strict Connective As Hyper Conceit On Super Con”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8080100). 1532
1533
1534
133. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Con By Hyper Conceit Of Reverse Strict Connective In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8080068). 1535
1536
1537
134. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Unequal Connective Dominating As Hyper Conceit On Super Con”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8078445). 1538
1539
1540
135. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Con By Hyper Conceit Of Unequal Connective Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8078543). 1541
1542
1543
136. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Strict Connective Dominating As Hyper Conceit On Super Con”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8076416). 1544
1545
1546
137. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Con By Hyper Conceit Of Strict Connective Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8076399). 1547
1548
1549
138. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Reverse Dimension Dominating As Hyper Dimple On Super Dimity”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8072171). 1550
1551
1552
139. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Dimity By Hyper Dimple Of Reverse Dimension Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8072267). 1553
1554
1555
140. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Equal Dimension Dominating As Hyper Dimple On Super Dimity”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8067384). 1556
1557
1558
141. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Dimity By Hyper Dimple Of Equal Dimension Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8067409). 1559
1560
1561
142. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Dimension Dominating As Hyper Dimple On Super Dimity”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8061927). 1562
1563
1564

143. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Dimity By Hyper Dimple Of Dimension Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8062016). 1565
1566
1567
144. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Reverse Connective Dominating As Hyper Conceit On Super Con”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8057696). 1568
1569
1570
145. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Con By Hyper Conceit Of Reverse Connective Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8057753). 1571
1572
1573
146. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Equal Connective Dominating As Hyper Conceit On Super Con”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8052893). 1574
1575
1576
147. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Con By Hyper Conceit Of Equal Connective Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8052925). 1577
1578
1579
148. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Connective Dominating As Hyper Conceit On Super Con”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8051346). 1580
1581
1582
149. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Con By Hyper Conceit Of Connective Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8051360). 1583
1584
1585
150. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By United Dominating As Hyper Ultra On Super Units”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8025707). 1586
1587
1588
151. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Units By Hyper Ultra Of United Dominating In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8027275). 1589
1590
1591
152. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Zero Forcing As Hyper ford On Super forceps”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8017246). 1592
1593
1594
153. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super forceps By Hyper ford Of Zero Forcing In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8020128). 1595
1596
1597
154. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Matrix-Based As Hyper mat On Super matte”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7978571). 1598
1599
1600
155. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super mat By Hyper matte Of Matrix-Based In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7978857). 1601
1602
1603
156. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Dominating-Edges As Hyper Dome On Super Eddy”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7940830). 1604
1605
1606
157. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Eddy By Hyper Dome Of Dominating-Edges In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7943578). 1607
1608
1609

158. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Edge-Gap As Hyper Gape On Super Gab”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7916595). 1610
1611
1612
159. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Gab By Hyper Gape Of Edge-Gap In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7923632). 1613
1614
1615
160. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Type-Cycle-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7904698). 1616
1617
1618
161. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Nebulous By Hyper Nebbish Of Eulerian-Type-Cycle-Neighbor In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7904671). 1619
1620
1621
162. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Type-Cycle-Decomposition As Hyper Decompress On Super Decomensation”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7904529). 1622
1623
1624
1625
163. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Decomensation By Hyper Decompress Of Eulerian-Type-Cycle-Decomposition In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7904401). 1626
1627
1628
1629
164. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Type-Cycle-Cut As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7871026). 1630
1631
1632
165. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Nebulous By Hyper Nebbish Of Eulerian-Type-Cycle-Cut In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7874647). 1633
1634
1635
166. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Cycle-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7857856). 1636
1637
1638
167. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Nebulous By Hyper Nebbish Of Eulerian-Cycle-Neighbor In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7857841). 1639
1640
1641
168. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Cycle-Decomposition As Hyper Decompress On Super Decomensation”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7855661). 1642
1643
1644
169. Henry Garrett, “New Ideas On Super Decomensation By Hyper Decompress Of Eulerian-Cycle-Decomposition In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7855637). 1645
1646
1647
170. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Cycle-Cut As Hyper Eulogy On Super EULA*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7853867). 1648
1649
1650
171. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super EULA By Hyper Eulogy Of Eulerian-Cycle-Cut In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7853922). 1651
1652
1653

172. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Type-Path-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7851519). 1654
1655
1656
173. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Nebulous By Hyper Nebbish Of Eulerian-Type-Path-Neighbor In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7851550). 1657
1658
1659
174. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Type-Path-Decomposition As Hyper Decompress On Super Decomensation*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7839333). 1660
1661
1662
175. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Decomensation By Hyper Decompress Of Eulerian-Type-Path-Decomposition In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7840206). 1663
1664
1665
176. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Type-Path-Cut As Hyper Eulogy On Super EULA*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7834229). 1666
1667
1668
177. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super EULA By Hyper Eulogy Of Eulerian-Type-Path-Cut In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7834261). 1669
1670
1671
178. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Path-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7824560). 1672
1673
1674
179. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Nebulous By Hyper Nebbish Of Eulerian-Path-Neighbor In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7824623). 1675
1676
1677
180. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Path-Decomposition As Hyper Decompress On Super Decomensation*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7819531). 1678
1679
1680
181. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Decomensation By Hyper Decompress Of Eulerian-Path-Decomposition In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7819579). 1681
1682
1683
182. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph As Hyper Tool On Super Toot*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7812236). 1684
1685
1686
183. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By initial Eulerian-Path-Cut As Hyper initial Eulogy On Super initial EULA*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7809365). 1687
1688
1689
184. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Path-Cut As Hyper Eulogy-Path-Cut On Super EULA-Path-Cut*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7809358). 1690
1691
1692
185. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super EULA By Hyper Eulogy Of Eulerian-Path-Cut In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7809219). 1693
1694
1695
186. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian-Path-Cut As Hyper Eulogy On Super EULA*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7809328). 1696
1697
1698

187. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Hamiltonian-Type-Cycle-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7806767). 1699
1700
1701
188. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Nebulous By Hyper Nebbish Of Hamiltonian-Type-Cycle-Neighbor In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7806838). 1702
1703
1704
189. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Hamiltonian-Type-Cycle-Decomposition As Hyper Decompress On Super Decomensation*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7804238). 1705
1706
1707
1708
190. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Decomensation By Hyper Decompress Of Hamiltonian-Type-Cycle-Decomposition In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7804228). 1709
1710
1711
191. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Hamiltonian-Type-Cycle-Cut As Hyper Hamper On Super Hammy*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7799902). 1712
1713
1714
192. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Hammy By Hyper Hamper Of Hamiltonian-Type-Cycle-Cut In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7804218). 1715
1716
1717
193. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Hamiltonian-Cycle-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7796334). 1718
1719
1720
194. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Hamiltonian-Cycle-Decomposition As Hyper Decompress On Super Decomensation*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7793372). 1721
1722
1723
195. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Hamiltonian-Cycle-Cut As Hyper Hamper On Super Hammy*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7791952). 1724
1725
1726
196. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Hammy By Hyper Hamper Of Hamiltonian-Cycle-Cut In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7791982). 1727
1728
1729
197. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Hamiltonian-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7790026). 1730
1731
1732
198. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Nebulous By Hyper Nebbish Of Hamiltonian-Neighbor In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7790052). 1733
1734
1735
199. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Hamiltonian-Decomposition As Hyper Decompress On Super Decomensation*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7787066). 1736
1737
1738
200. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Decomensation By Hyper Decompress Of Hamiltonian-Decomposition In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7787094). 1739
1740
1741

201. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Hamiltonian-Cut As Hyper Hamper On Super Hammy*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7781476). 1742
1743
1744
202. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Hammy By Hyper Hamper Of Hamiltonian-Cut In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7783082). 1745
1746
1747
203. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Recognition of Cancer And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Trace-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7777857). 1748
1749
1750
204. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Nebulous By Hyper Nebbish Of Trace-Neighbor In Recognition of Cancer With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7779286). 1751
1752
1753
205. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Trace-Decomposition As Hyper Decompress On Super Decomensation*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7771831). 1754
1755
1756
206. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Decomensation By Hyper Decompress Of Trace-Decomposition In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7772468). 1757
1758
1759
207. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Trace-Cut As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.20913.25446). 1760
1761
1762
208. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Tract By Hyper Track Of Trace-Cut In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, Zenodo 2023, (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7764916). 1763
1764
1765
209. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Edge-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.11770.98247). 1766
1767
1768
210. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Nebulous By Hyper Nebbish Of Edge-Neighbor In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.12400.12808). 1769
1770
1771
211. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Edge-Decomposition As Hyper Decompress On Super Decomensation*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.22545.10089). 1772
1773
1774
212. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Decomensation By Hyper Decompress Of Edge-Decomposition In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.29544.34564). 1775
1776
1777
213. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Edge-Cut As Hyper Edify On Super Eddy*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.11377.76644). 1778
1779
1780
214. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Eddy By Hyper Edify Of Edge-Cut In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23750.96329). 1781
1782
1783
215. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Vertex-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.31366.24641). 1784
1785
1786

216. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Nebulous By Hyper Nebbish Of Vertex-Neighbor In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.34721.68960). 1787
1788
1789
217. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Vertex-Decomposition As Hyper Decompress On Super Decomensation*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.30212.81289). 1790
1791
1792
218. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Decomensation By Hyper Decompress Of Vertex-Decomposition In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.18468.76169). 1793
1794
1795
219. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Vertex-Cut As Hyper Vertu On Super Vertigo*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.24288.35842). 1796
1797
1798
220. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Vertigo By Hyper Vertu Of Vertex-Cut In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.32467.25124). 1799
1800
1801
221. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Stable-Neighbor As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.31025.45925). 1802
1803
1804
222. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Nebulizer By Hyper Nub Of Stable-Neighbor In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.17184.25602). 1805
1806
1807
223. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Stable-Decompositions As Hyper Stain On Super Stagy*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23423.28327). 1808
1809
1810
224. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Stale By Hyper Stalk Of Stable-Decompositions In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.28456.44805). 1811
1812
1813
225. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Stable-Cut As Hyper Stain On Super Stagy*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23525.68320). 1814
1815
1816
226. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Stale By Hyper Stalk Of Stable-Cut In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.20170.24000). 1817
1818
1819
227. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Clique-Neighbors As Hyper Nebbish On Super Nebulous*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.36475.59683). 1820
1821
1822
228. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Nebulizer By Hyper Nub Of Clique-Neighbors In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.29764.71046). 1823
1824
1825
229. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Clique-Decompositions As Hyper Decompile On Super Decommission*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.18780.87683). 1826
1827
1828
230. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Decomensation By Hyper Decompress Of Clique- Decompositions In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.27169.48487). 1829
1830
1831

231. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Clique-Cut As Hyper Click On Super Cliche*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.26134.01603). 1832
1833
1834
232. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Cliff By Hyper Cling Of Clique-Cut In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.27392.30721). 1835
1836
1837
233. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Space As Hyper Spin On Super Spacy*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.33028.40321). 1838
1839
1840
234. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By List- Coloring As Hyper List On Super Lisle*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.21389.20966). 1841
1842
1843
235. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Lith By Hyper Lite Of List-Coloring In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.16356.04489). 1844
1845
1846
236. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Space As Hyper Sparse On Super Spark*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.21756.21129). 1847
1848
1849
237. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Solidarity By Hyper Soul Of Space In Cancer’s Recognition With (Extreme) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.30983.68009). 1850
1851
1852
238. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Edge-Connectivity As Hyper Disclosure On Super Closure*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.28552.29445). 1853
1854
1855
239. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Uniform By Hyper Deformation Of Edge-Connectivity In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.10936.21761). 1856
1857
1858
240. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Vertex-Connectivity As Hyper Leak On Super Structure*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.35105.89447). 1859
1860
1861
241. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super System By Hyper Explosions Of Vertex-Connectivity In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.30072.72960). 1862
1863
1864
242. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Tree-Decomposition As Hyper Forward On Super Returns*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.31147.52003). 1865
1866
1867
243. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Nodes By Hyper Moves Of Tree-Decomposition In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.32825.24163). 1868
1869
1870
244. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Chord As Hyper Excellence On Super Excess*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.13059.58401). 1871
1872
1873
245. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Gap By Hyper Navigations Of Chord In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.11172.14720). 1874
1875
1876

246. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyper(i,j)-Domination As Hyper Controller On Super Waves*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.22011.80165). 1877
1878
1879
247. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Coincidence By Hyper Routes Of SuperHyper(i,j)-Domination In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.30819.84003). 1880
1881
1882
248. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperEdge-Domination As Hyper Reversion On Super Indirection*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.10493.84962). 1883
1884
1885
249. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Obstacles By Hyper Model Of SuperHyperEdge-Domination In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.13849.29280). 1886
1887
1888
250. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperK-Domination As Hyper k-Actions On Super Patterns*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.19944.14086). 1889
1890
1891
251. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Harmony By Hyper k-Function Of SuperHyperK-Domination In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23299.58404). 1892
1893
1894
252. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperK-Number As Hyper k-Partition On Super Layers*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.33103.76968). 1895
1896
1897
253. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Gradient By Hyper k-Class Of SuperHyperK-Number In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23037.44003). 1898
1899
1900
254. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperOrder As Hyper Enumerations On Super Landmarks*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.35646.56641). 1901
1902
1903
255. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Analogous By Hyper Visions Of SuperHyperOrder In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.18030.48967). 1904
1905
1906
256. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperColoring As Hyper Categories On Super Neighbors*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.13973.81121). 1907
1908
1909
257. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Relations By Hyper Identifications Of SuperHyperColoring In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.34106.47047). 1910
1911
1912
258. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Contradiction By Hyper Detection of SuperHyperDefensive In Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.13397.09446). 1913
1914
1915
259. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperDimension As Hyper Distinguishing On Super Distances*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.31956.88961). 1916
1917
1918
260. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Locations By Hyper Differing Of SuperHyperDimension In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.15179.67361). 1919
1920
1921

261. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperDominating As Hyper Closing On Super Messy*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.21510.45125). 1922
1923
1924
262. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Missing By Hyper Searching Of SuperHyperDominating In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.13121.84321). 1925
1926
1927
263. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperConnected As Hyper Group On Super Surge*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.11758.69441). 1928
1929
1930
264. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Outbreak By Hyper Collections Of SuperHyperConnected In Cancer’s Recognition With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.31891.35367). 1931
1932
1933
265. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperTotal As Hyper Covering On Super Infections*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.19360.87048). 1934
1935
1936
266. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Extremism By Hyper Treatments Of SuperHyperTotal In Cancer’s Recognition with (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.32363.21286). 1937
1938
1939
267. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Isolation By Hyper Perfectness Of SuperHyperPerfect In Cancer’s Recognition with (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23266.81602). 1940
1941
1942
268. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperPerfect As Hyper Idealism On Super Vacancy*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.19911.37285). 1943
1944
1945
269. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition And Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperJoin As Hyper Separations On Super Sorts*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.11050.90569). 1946
1947
1948
270. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super connections By Hyper disconnections Of SuperHyperJoin In Cancer’s Recognition with (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.17761.79206). 1949
1950
1951
271. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Mixed-Devastations By Hyper Decisions Of SuperHyperDuality In Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.34953.52320). 1952
1953
1954
272. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition As (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperDuality As Hyper Imaginations On Super Mixed-Illustrations*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.33275.80161). 1955
1956
1957
273. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas In Cancer’s Recognition As (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph By Path SuperHyperColoring As Hyper Correction On Super Faults*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.30182.50241). 1958
1959
1960
274. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Reflections By Hyper Rotations Of Path SuperHyperColoring In Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.33459.30243). 1961
1962
1963
275. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas As Hyper Deformations On Super Chains In Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperDensity*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.13444.60806). 1964
1965
1966

276. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas As Hyper Ignorance By SuperHyperDensity On Super Resistances In Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi:10.13140/RG.2.2.16800.05123). 1967
1968
1969
277. Henry Garrett, “*New Research On Cancer’s Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian SuperHyperCycles and Hamiltonian Sets As Hyper Covering Versus Super separations-VI*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.29913.80482). 1970
1971
1972
1973
278. Henry Garrett, “*New Research On Cancer’s Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian SuperHyperCycles and Hamiltonian Sets As Hyper Covering Versus Super separations-V*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.33269.24809). 1974
1975
1976
1977
279. Henry Garrett, “*New Research On Cancer’s Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian SuperHyperCycles and Hamiltonian Sets As Hyper Covering Versus Super separations-IV*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.34946.96960). 1978
1979
1980
1981
280. Henry Garrett, “*A Research On Cancer’s Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian SuperHyperCycles and Hamiltonian Sets As Hyper Covering Versus Super separations-III*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.14814.31040). 1982
1983
1984
1985
281. Henry Garrett, “*A Research On Cancer’s Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian SuperHyperCycles and Hamiltonian Sets As Hyper Covering Versus Super separations-II*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.15653.17125). 1986
1987
1988
1989
282. Henry Garrett, “*A Research On Cancer’s Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Eulerian SuperHyperCycles and Hamiltonian Sets As Hyper Covering Versus Super separations-I*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.25719.50089). 1990
1991
1992
1993
283. Henry Garrett, “*New Ideas On Super Disruptions In Cancer’s Extreme Recognition As Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By Hyper Plans Called SuperHyperConnectivities*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.29441.94562). 1994
1995
1996
1997
284. Henry Garrett, “*Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition As Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph By SuperHyperConnectivities As Hyper Diagnosis On Super Mechanism*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.17252.24968). 1998
1999
2000
285. Henry Garrett, “*Cancer’s Recognition and (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph By the Criteria of Eulerian and Hamiltonian Type-Sets As Hyper Modified Cycles On Super Mess*”, ResearchGate 2023,(doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.16652.59525). 2001
2002
2003
286. Henry Garrett, “*Eulerian and Hamiltonian In Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph On Super Interactions By Hyper Extensions of Cycles*”, ResearchGate 2023,(doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.34583.24485). 2004
2005
2006
287. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperGirth Type-Results on extreme SuperHyperGirth theory and (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs Toward Cancer’s extreme Recognition*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010396 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0396.v1). 2007
2008
2009
2010

288. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Warns Hyper Landmark of neutrosophic SuperHyperGirth In Super Type-Versions of Cancer’s neutrosophic Recognition*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010395 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0395.v1). 2011
2012
2013
2014
289. Henry Garrett, “*The Constructions of (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs on the Cancer’s Recognition in The Confrontation With Super Attacks In Hyper Situations By Implementing (Neutrosophic) 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in The Technical Approaches to Neutralize SuperHyperViews*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.26240.51204). 2015
2016
2017
2018
2019
290. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing As the Entrepreneurs on Cancer’s Recognitions To Fail Forcing Style As the Super Classes With Hyper Effects In The Background of the Framework is So-Called (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.12818.73925). 2020
2021
2022
2023
2024
291. Henry Garrett, “*Super Actions On The Types of Hyper Levels In The Sensible Neutrosophic SuperHyperGirth On Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023,(doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.26836.88960). 2025
2026
2027
2028
292. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperGirth Approaches on the Super Challenges on the Cancer’s Recognition In the Hyper Model of (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2023,(doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.36745.93289). 2029
2030
2031
293. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperClique as the Firm Scheme of Confrontation under Cancer’s Recognition as the Model in The Setting of (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010308 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0308.v1). 2032
2033
2034
2035
294. Henry Garrett, “*Uncertainty On The Act And Effect Of Cancer Alongside The Foggy Positions Of Cells Toward Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperClique inside Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs Titled Cancer’s Recognition*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010282 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0282.v1). 2036
2037
2038
2039
295. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Version Of Separates Groups Of Cells In Cancer’s Recognition On Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010267 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0267.v1).). 2040
2041
2042
296. Henry Garrett, “*The Shift Paradigm To Classify Separately The Cells and Affected Cells Toward The Totality Under Cancer’s Recognition By New Multiple Definitions On the Sets Polynomials Alongside Numbers In The (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperMatching Theory Based on SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010265 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0265.v1). 2043
2044
2045
2046
2047
2048
297. Henry Garrett, “*Breaking the Continuity and Uniformity of Cancer In The Worst Case of Full Connections With Extreme Failed SuperHyperClique In Cancer’s Recognition Applied in (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010262,(doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0262.v1). 2049
2050
2051
2052
298. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperStable as the Survivors on the Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition Based on Uncertainty to All Modes in Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010240 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0240.v1). 2053
2054
2055
2056

299. Henry Garrett, “*Extremism of the Attacked Body Under the Cancer’s Circumstances Where Cancer’s Recognition Titled (Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs)*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010224, (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0224.v1). 2057
2058
2059
2060
300. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperMatching By (R-)Definitions And Polynomials To Monitor Cancer’s Recognition In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.35061.65767). 2061
2062
2063
301. Henry Garrett, “*The Focus on The Partitions Obtained By Parallel Moves In The Cancer’s Extreme Recognition With Different Types of Extreme SuperHyperMatching Set and Polynomial on (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.18494.15680). 2064
2065
2066
2067
302. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme Failed SuperHyperClique Decides the Failures on the Cancer’s Recognition in the Perfect Connections of Cancer’s Attacks By SuperHyperModels Named (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.32530.73922). 2068
2069
2070
2071
303. Henry Garrett, “*Indeterminacy On The All Possible Connections of Cells In Front of Cancer’s Attacks In The Terms of Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperClique on Cancer’s Recognition called Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.15897.70243). 2072
2073
2074
2075
304. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme Failed SuperHyperClique Decides the Failures on the Cancer’s Recognition in the Perfect Connections of Cancer’s Attacks By SuperHyperModels Named (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.32530.73922). 2076
2077
2078
2079
305. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010105 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0105.v1). 2080
2081
2082
306. Henry Garrett, “*Perfect Directions Toward Idealism in Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition Forwarding Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.30092.80004). 2083
2084
2085
307. Henry Garrett, “*Demonstrating Complete Connections in Every Embedded Regions and Sub-Regions in the Terms of Cancer’s Recognition and (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperClique*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23172.19849). 2086
2087
2088
2089
308. Henry Garrett, “*Basic Notions on (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperForcing And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010105 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0105.v1). 2090
2091
2092
2093
309. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010088 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0088.v1). 2094
2095
2096
2097
310. Henry Garrett, “*Different Neutrosophic Types of Neutrosophic Regions titled neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperStable in Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition modeled in the Form of Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.17385.36968). 2098
2099
2100
2101

311. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in the SuperHyperFunction To Use Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition And Beyond*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010044 2102
2103
2104
312. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperStable on Cancer’s Recognition by Well- SuperHyperModelled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, Preprints 2023, 2023010043 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202301.0043.v1). 2105
2106
2107
313. Henry Garrett, “*Using the Tool As (Neutrosophic) Failed SuperHyperStable To SuperHyperModel Cancer’s Recognition Titled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.28945.92007). 2108
2109
2110
314. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Messy-Style SuperHyperGraphs To Form Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable To Act on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognitions In Special ViewPoints*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.11447.80803). 2111
2112
2113
315. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperStable on Cancer’s Recognition by Well-SuperHyperModelled (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2023, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.35774.77123). 2114
2115
2116
316. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in the SuperHyperFunction To Use Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs on Cancer’s Neutrosophic Recognition And Beyond*”, ResearchGate 2022, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.36141.77287). 2117
2118
2119
2120
317. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) 1-Failed SuperHyperForcing in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2022, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.29430.88642). 2121
2122
2123
318. Henry Garrett, “*Basic Notions on (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperForcing And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling in Cancer’s Recognitions And (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraphs*”, ResearchGate 2022, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.11369.16487). 2124
2125
2126
2127
319. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions Featuring (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperAlliances*”, Preprints 2022, 2022120549 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0549.v1). 2128
2129
2130
320. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions Featuring (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperDefensive SuperHyperAlliances*”, ResearchGate 2022, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.19380.94084). 2131
2132
2133
321. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperAlliances With SuperHyperDefensive and SuperHyperOffensive Type-SuperHyperSet On (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions And Related (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperClasses*”, Preprints 2022, 2022120540 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0540.v1). 2134
2135
2136
2137
2138
322. Henry Garrett, “*(Neutrosophic) SuperHyperAlliances With SuperHyperDefensive and SuperHyperOffensive Type-SuperHyperSet On (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperGraph With (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions And Related (Neutrosophic) SuperHyperClasses*”, ResearchGate 2022, (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.14426.41923). 2139
2140
2141
2142
2143
323. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperGirth on SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions*”, Preprints 2022, 2022120500 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0500.v1). 2144
2145
2146

324. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperGirth on SuperHyperGraph and Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph With SuperHyperModeling of Cancer’s Recognitions*”, ResearchGate 2022 (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.20993.12640). 2147
2148
2149
325. Henry Garrett, “*Some SuperHyperDegrees and Co-SuperHyperDegrees on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs and SuperHyperGraphs Alongside Applications in Cancer’s Treatments*”, Preprints 2022, 2022120324 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202212.0324.v1). 2150
2151
2152
2153
326. Henry Garrett, “*Some SuperHyperDegrees and Co-SuperHyperDegrees on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs And SuperHyperGraphs Alongside Applications in Cancer’s Treatments*”, ResearchGate 2022 (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23123.04641). 2154
2155
2156
2157
327. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperDominating and SuperHyperResolving on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs And Their Directions in Game Theory and Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses*”, Preprints 2022, 2022110576 (doi: 10.20944/preprints202211.0576.v1). 2158
2159
2160
2161
328. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperDominating and SuperHyperResolving on Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs And Their Directions in Game Theory and Neutrosophic SuperHyperClasses*”, ResearchGate 2022 (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.23324.56966). 2162
2163
2164
2165
329. Henry Garrett, “*Basic Neutrosophic Notions Concerning SuperHyperDominating and Neutrosophic SuperHyperResolving in SuperHyperGraph*”, ResearchGate 2022 (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.29173.86244). 2166
2167
2168
330. Henry Garrett, “*Initial Material of Neutrosophic Preliminaries to Study Some Neutrosophic Notions Based on Neutrosophic SuperHyperEdge (NSHE) in Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraph (NSHG)*”, ResearchGate 2022 (doi: 10.13140/RG.2.2.25385.88160). 2169
2170
2171
2172
331. Henry Garrett, ”PAIRED-DOMINATION In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14577256). 2173
2174
332. Henry Garrett, ”EQUALITY CO-NEIGHBORHOOD DOMINATING SET In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14562725). 2175
2176
2177
333. Henry Garrett, ”STRONGLY-DOMINATING SET In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14544008). 2178
2179
334. Henry Garrett, ”DOUBLY CONNECTED DOMINATION In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14527741). 2180
2181
335. Henry Garrett, ”RESTRAINED DOMINATION In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14497269). 2182
2183
336. Henry Garrett, ”Dom-forcing In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.14175736). 2184
2185
337. Henry Garrett, ”Diamond search Edge In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13600433). 2186
2187
338. Henry Garrett, ”Triangle-free search Edge In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13594674). 2188
2189

339. Henry Garrett, "Diamond search In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13525750). 2190
2191
340. Henry Garrett, "Triangle-free search In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13512157). 2192
2193
341. Henry Garrett, "Edge Cover In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13376543). 2194
2195
342. Henry Garrett, "Vertex Cover In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.13294466). 2196
2197
343. Henry Garrett, "Burning Number In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12797511). 2198
2199
344. Henry Garrett, "Zero Forcing In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12691570). 2200
2201
345. Henry Garrett, "Dual Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs 6". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12651785). 2202
2203
346. Henry Garrett, "Dual Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs 5". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.12214087). 2204
2205
347. Henry Garrett, "Dual Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs 4". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11876996). 2206
2207
348. Henry Garrett, "Dual Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs 3". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11529821). 2208
2209
349. Henry Garrett, "Dual Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs 2". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11398118). 2210
2211
350. Henry Garrett, "Dual Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs 1". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.11106891). 2212
2213
351. Henry Garrett, "Perfect Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs 3". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10946745). 2214
2215
352. Henry Garrett, "Perfect Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs 2". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2024 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10909931). 2216
2217
353. Henry Garrett, "Perfect Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10871136). 2218
2219
354. Henry Garrett, "Stable Sequence In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10523307). 2220
2221
355. Henry Garrett, "Resolving Sequence In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10395711). 2222
2223
356. Henry Garrett, "Dominating Sequence In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.10042973). 2224
2225
357. Henry Garrett, "Stable In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8210033). 2226
2227
358. Henry Garrett, "Reverse Connective Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8206898). 2228
2229

359. Henry Garrett, "Equal Connective Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8201378). 2230
2231
360. Henry Garrett, "Connective Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8194003). 2232
2233
361. Henry Garrett, "Domination In Neutrosophic SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8113416). 2234
2235
362. Henry Garrett, "SuperHyperPerfect Search In SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8104880). 2236
2237
363. Henry Garrett, "Reverse Strict Dimension Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8092816). 2238
2239
364. Henry Garrett, "Unequal Dimension Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8090194). 2240
2241
365. Henry Garrett, "Strict Dimension Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8086310). 2242
2243
366. Henry Garrett, "Reverse Strict Connective In SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8080167). 2244
2245
367. Henry Garrett, "Unequal Connective Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8078574). 2246
2247
368. Henry Garrett, "Strict Connective Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8076449). 2248
2249
369. Henry Garrett, "Reverse Dimension Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8072310). 2250
2251
370. Henry Garrett, "Equal Dimension Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8067469). 2252
2253
371. Henry Garrett, "Dimension Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8062076). 2254
2255
372. Henry Garrett, "Reverse Connective Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8057817). 2256
2257
373. Henry Garrett, "Equal Connective Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8052976). 2258
2259
374. Henry Garrett, "Connective Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8051368). 2260
2261
375. Henry Garrett, "United Dominating In SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8027488). 2262
2263
376. Henry Garrett, "Zero Forcing In SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.8020181). 2264
2265
377. Henry Garrett, "Matrix-Based In SuperHyperGraphs". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7978921). 2266
2267
378. Henry Garrett, "Collections of Math II". Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7943878). 2268
2269

379. Henry Garrett, “Dominating-Edges In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7943871). 2270
2271
380. Henry Garrett, “Edge-Gap In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7923786). 2272
2273
381. Henry Garrett, “Eulerian-Type-Cycle-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7905287). 2274
2275
382. Henry Garrett, “Eulerian-Type-Cycle-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7904586). 2276
2277
383. Henry Garrett, “Eulerian-Type-Cycle-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7874677). 2278
2279
384. Henry Garrett, “Eulerian-Cycle-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7857906). 2280
2281
385. Henry Garrett, “Eulerian-Cycle-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7856329). 2282
2283
386. Henry Garrett, “*Eulerian-Cycle-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7854561). 2284
2285
387. Henry Garrett, “*Eulerian-Type-Path-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7851893). 2286
2287
388. Henry Garrett, “*Eulerian-Type-Path-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7848019). 2288
2289
389. Henry Garrett, “*Eulerian-Type-Path-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7835063). 2290
2291
390. Henry Garrett, “*Eulerian-Path-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7826705). 2292
2293
391. Henry Garrett, “*Eulerian-Path-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7820680). 2294
2295
392. Henry Garrett, “*Eulerian-Path-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7812750). 2296
2297
393. Henry Garrett, “*Hamiltonian-Type-Cycle-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7812142). 2298
2299
394. Henry Garrett, “*Hamiltonian-Type-Cycle-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7810394). 2300
2301
395. Henry Garrett, “*Hamiltonian-Type-Cycle-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7807782). 2302
2303
396. Henry Garrett, “*Hamiltonian-Cycle-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7804449). 2304
2305
397. Henry Garrett, “*Hamiltonian-Cycle-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7793875). 2306
2307
398. Henry Garrett, “*Hamiltonian-Cycle-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7792307). 2308
2309

- 399. Henry Garrett, “*Hamiltonian-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7790728). 2310
2311
- 400. Henry Garrett, “*Hamiltonian-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7787712). 2312
2313
- 401. Henry Garrett, “*Hamiltonian-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7783791). 2314
2315
- 402. Henry Garrett, “*Trace-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7780123). 2316
2317
- 403. Henry Garrett, “*Trace-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7773119). 2318
2319
- 404. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperDuality*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7637762). 2320
2321
- 405. Henry Garrett, “*Trace-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7766174). 2322
2323
- 406. Henry Garrett, “*Edge-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7762232). 2324
2325
- 407. Henry Garrett, “*Edge-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7758601). 2326
2327
- 408. Henry Garrett, “*Edge-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7754661). 2328
2329
- 409. Henry Garrett, “*Vertex-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7750995) . 2330
2331
- 410. Henry Garrett, “*Vertex-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7749875). 2332
2333
- 411. Henry Garrett, “*Vertex-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7747236). 2334
2335
- 412. Henry Garrett, “*Stable-Neighbor In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7742587). 2336
2337
- 413. Henry Garrett, “*Stable-Decompositions In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7738635). 2338
2339
- 414. Henry Garrett, “*Stable-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7734719). 2340
2341
- 415. Henry Garrett, “*Clique-Neighbors In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7730484). 2342
2343
- 416. Henry Garrett, “*Clique-Decompositions In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7730469). 2344
2345
- 417. Henry Garrett, “*Clique-Cut In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7722865). 2346
2347
- 418. Henry Garrett, “*Space In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7713563). 2348
2349

419. Henry Garrett, “*Space In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7709116). 2350
2351
420. Henry Garrett, “*Edge-Connectivity In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7706415). 2352
2353
421. Henry Garrett, “*Vertex-Connectivity In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7706063). 2354
2355
422. Henry Garrett, “*Tree-Decomposition In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7701906). 2356
2357
423. Henry Garrett, “*Chord In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7700205). 2358
2359
424. Henry Garrett, “*(i,j)-Domination In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7694876). 2360
2361
425. Henry Garrett, “*Edge-Domination In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7679410). 2362
2363
426. Henry Garrett, “*K-Domination In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7675982). 2364
2365
427. Henry Garrett, “*K-Number In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7672388). 2366
2367
428. Henry Garrett, “*Order In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7668648). 2368
2369
429. Henry Garrett, “*Coloring In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7662810). 2370
2371
430. Henry Garrett, “*Dimension In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7659162). 2372
2373
431. Henry Garrett, “*Cancer In SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7653233). 2374
2375
432. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperWheel*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7653204). 2376
2377
433. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperMultipartite*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7653142). 2378
2379
434. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperBipartite*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7653117). 2380
2381
435. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperStar*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7653089). 2382
2383
436. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperCycle*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7651687). 2384
2385
437. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperPath*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7651619). 2386
2387
438. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperDomination*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7651439). 2388
2389

439. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperDominating*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7650729). 2390
2391
440. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperConnected*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7647868). 2392
2393
441. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperTotal*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7647017). 2394
2395
442. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperPerfect*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7644894). 2396
2397
443. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperJoin*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7641880). 2398
2399
444. Henry Garrett, “*Path SuperHyperColoring*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7632923). 2400
2401
445. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperDensity*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7623459). 2402
2403
446. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic SuperHyperConnectivities*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7606416). 2404
2405
447. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperConnectivities*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7606416). 2406
2407
448. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperConnectivities*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7606404). 2408
2409
449. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic SuperHyperCycle*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7580018). 2410
2411
450. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperCycle*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7580018). 2412
2413
451. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperCycle*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7580018). 2414
2415
452. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperCycle*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7579929). 2416
2417
453. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic SuperHyperGirth*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7563170). 2418
2419
454. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperGirth*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7563164). 2420
2421
455. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperGirth*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7563160). 2422
2423
456. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperGirth*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7563160). 2424
2425
457. Henry Garrett, “*Overlook On SuperHyperGirth*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7563160). 2426
2427
458. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic SuperHyperMatching*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7557063). 2428
2429

459. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperMatching*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7557009). 2430
2431
460. Henry Garrett, “*Overlook On SuperHyperMatching*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7539484). 2432
2433
461. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperClique*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7523390). 2434
2435
462. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme Failed SuperHyperClique*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7523390). 2436
2437
463. Henry Garrett, “*Overlook On Failed SuperHyperClique*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7523390). 2438
2439
464. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperClique*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7574952). 2440
2441
465. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic SuperHyperClique*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7574992). 2442
2443
466. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperClique*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7523357). 2444
2445
467. Henry Garrett, “*Overlook On SuperHyperClique*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7523357). 2446
2447
468. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperStable*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7504782). 2448
2449
469. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme Failed SuperHyperStable*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7504782). 2450
2451
470. Henry Garrett, “*Overlook On Failed SuperHyperStable*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7504782). 2452
2453
471. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic SuperHyperStable*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7499395). 2454
2455
472. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperStable*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7499395). 2456
2457
473. Henry Garrett, “*Overlook On SuperHyperStable*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7499395). 2458
2459
474. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Failed SuperHyperForcing*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7497450). 2460
2461
475. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme Failed SuperHyperForcing*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7497450). 2462
2463
476. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic SuperHyperForcing*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7494862). 2464
2465
477. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperForcing*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7494862). 2466
2467
478. Henry Garrett, “*Overlook On SuperHyperForcing*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7494862). 2468
2469

479. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic SuperHyperAlliances*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7493845). 2470
2471
480. Henry Garrett, “*Extreme SuperHyperAlliances*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7493845). 2472
2473
481. Henry Garrett, “*Overlook On SuperHyperAlliances*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7493845). 2474
2475
482. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperMatching*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7539484). 2476
2477
483. Henry Garrett, “*Failed SuperHyperClique*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7523390). 2478
2479
484. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperClique*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7523357). 2480
2481
485. Henry Garrett, “*Failed SuperHyperStable*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7504782). 2482
2483
486. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperStable*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7499395). 2484
2485
487. Henry Garrett, “*Failed SuperHyperForcing*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7497450). 2486
2487
488. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperForcing*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7494862). 2488
2489
489. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperAlliances*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7493845). 2490
2491
490. Henry Garrett, “*SuperHyperGraphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7480110). 2492
2493
491. Henry Garrett, “*Neut. SuperHyperEdges*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.7378758). 2494
2495
492. Henry Garrett, “*Beyond Neutrosophic Graphs*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.6320305). 2496
2497
493. Henry Garrett, “*Neutrosophic Duality*”. Dr. Henry Garrett, 2023 (doi: 10.5281/zenodo.6677173). 2498
2499